

An insight into the active sites of the catalytic basic protein subunit PB1 of the RNA polymerase of human influenza viruses

Peramachi Palanivelu *

Department of Molecular Microbiology, School of Biotechnology, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai –625 021, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(01), 625–656

Publication history: Received on 09 December 2022; revised on 17 January 2023; accepted on 20 January 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.1.0109>

Abstract

RNA polymerase from human influenza viruses is a heterotrimeric enzyme and performs the crucial functions of both transcription and replication for multiplication of the viruses in human cells. The heterotrimeric enzyme is made up of two basic protein subunits (PB1 and PB2) and an acidic protein subunit (PA). All the three subunits perform well-defined function(s) in the transcription and replication processes in the human cells. The basic protein subunit PB1 is shown to possess the polymerization activity, whereas the PB2 and the PA subunits are found to be involved in the cap-snatching and proofreading (PR) activities, respectively. The polymerase activity in the catalytic subunit, PB1, is found to be an RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp). Multiple sequence alignment (MSA) analysis of the PB1 subunits from all the three human influenza viruses, A, B and C shows large number of highly conserved peptides, amino acid motifs and invariant amino acids. Site-directed mutagenesis (SDM) analysis and X-ray crystallographic data have shown that two completely conserved motifs, viz. –GDN- and –SDD-, are involved in binding to the catalytic Mg^{2+} ion. These data are in close agreement with the MSA analysis data of the polymerases from all the three human influenza viruses. Furthermore, two highly conserved polymerase catalytic regions are identified in the PB1 subunits by sequence similarity to other DNA/RNA polymerases and hence, are proposed to function in the nucleotidyl transfer activities. Presence of the two catalytic regions suggest that the polymerase may function in a dual mode, i.e., in phase I, in association with the cap-snatching subunit PB2, it could be involved in the synthesis of mRNAs (transcription mode) and once enough proteins are made from the mRNAs, in the second phase, in association with PR exonuclease subunit PA, it could switch to the replication mode to synthesize error-free, exact copies of the viral genome. For both the activities, it could use the same invariant catalytic Mg^{2+} -binding –GDN- and –SDD- motifs.

Keywords: Human Influenza viruses; RNA polymerase; Polymerase Basic Protein subunit PB1; Catalytic Metal-binding motifs; Polymerase active sites; Mechanism of action

1. Introduction

A large number of human and animal viral pathogens belong to RNA viruses. They cause major global health-care crisis and unprecedented economic losses. Attempts have been made to prepare vaccines and synthesize novel antivirals to contain the spread of these viruses. Whereas the vaccines are targeted mainly to the viral surface protein(s), the antivirals are targeted to the crucial enzymes that are involved in the lifecycle of these viruses. As all RNA viruses employ the crucial enzyme, viz. the RdRp for their multiplication in human cells, most of the antiviral drugs are targeted to this enzyme. As the RdRps perform both the transcription and replication processes in these RNA viruses (except retro viruses), the RdRps have been the main target for antiviral drug development to control the spread of RNA viral pathogens, in general. However, these efforts are hindered by limited structural information on the RdRp catalytic core(s) and its catalytic mechanism. In this analysis, attempts are made to understand the catalytic core(s) of this polymerase from all the three human influenza viruses and its possible catalytic mechanism.

* Corresponding author: Peramachi Palanivelu

Influenza, commonly known as "the flu", is an infectious disease caused by influenza viruses which also belong to (-) strand RNA viruses. Influenza viral infection is an airborne, highly contagious disease that generally causes acute respiratory illness resulting in variable degrees of systemic symptoms from mild fatigue to respiratory failure and death. Therefore, influenza viral infections have become a major public health-care concern worldwide. The influenza viruses are enveloped viruses of 150–200 nm diameter and belong to the family, Orthomyxoviridae. Out of the four genera (A–D) only influenza A, B and C viruses infect humans and the D virus infects livestock. Among them, infection by influenza A virus is the most dangerous and is the causative agent for the worldwide flu pandemics. For example, influenza A virus has caused four pandemics so far that have occurred in the last 100 years; in 1918, 1957, 1968 and 2009. Both influenza B and A viruses are also reported to cause seasonal epidemics each year and affect approximately 5–10% of the adult and 20–30% of the pediatric population. According to the World Health Organization, influenza epidemics lead to 3–5 million cases of severe illness and ~2,90,000–6,50,000 respiratory deaths each year (This estimate does not take into account of deaths from other diseases such as cardiovascular disease, which can be influenza-related). While influenza A virus shows animal to human transmissions, influenza B and C viruses show very limited host range and appear predominantly in humans [1]. Out of the three human influenza viruses, only the influenza A and B viruses cause substantial morbidity and mortality in humans, whereas the influenza C virus does not cause epidemics/pandemics, but is involved in sporadic outbreaks, causing only mild upper respiratory infections [2]. In contrast to influenza A virus, influenza B and C viruses do not have animal reservoirs, [3] suggesting the pandemic nature of the influenza A virus. Their genomic structure, surface proteins, serotypes, transcription and replication processes are already described by Palanivelu [4].

1.1. Salient Features of the Human Influenza Viral RNA Polymerases

Influenza viruses are (-) strand RNA viruses and replicated by the viral RNA (vRNA) polymerase in the host cell nucleus. Within a viral ribonucleotide particle (vRNP), a single RNA polymerase captures both the 3'- and 5'-termini of the viral RNA (vRNA) and forms a pseudo-circularized structure of the vRNA. The viral RNA polymerase is a heterotrimer and all three subunits are shown to perform well-defined function(s) in viral transcription and replication processes. For example, the PB1 subunit performs the polymerizing function, the PB2 subunit performs the cap-snatching function for priming the mRNA transcriptions [4] and the PA subunit has been suggested to perform the PR exonuclease function [5].

Though the RNA viruses are highly divergent in nature, but their key enzyme, i.e., the RdRp, is structurally and functionally very similar. For example, all the RdRps exhibit a characteristic cupped right-hand structure with the three major domains, viz. fingers, palm and thumb, similar to DNA-dependent DNA polymerases (DdDps) and many DNA-dependent RNA polymerases (DdRps). The X-ray crystallographic structures of the complete heterotrimeric viral polymerase have been reported by many investigators [6–8]. The X-ray structures revealed the PB1 subunits of the flu polymerases also showed the canonical closed right-handed fold, possessing the typical fingers, palm, and thumb domains [6–8]. Furthermore, the polymerase forms a compact structure with PB1 at its centre, capped on one face by PB2 and clamped between the two globular domains of the PA [6–8] (Fig. 1)

Figure 1 A schematic diagram showing the various subunits of the influenza viral polymerase. (The number of amino acids are given in brackets and are from influenza A virus)

Adapted from Pflug et al. and Fan et al. [6,8]

Figure 2 Domain Architecture of the PB1 catalytic subunit of the RNA polymerase from human influenza A virus.

NTD, N-terminal domain; CTD, C-terminal domain; (K235, K237 and R239 form the finger priming loop); Palm (K308, K480 and K481, G304, D305, N306, S444, D445, D446; the Mg²⁺-binding ⁻³⁰⁴GDN- and ⁻⁴⁴⁴SDD- motifs are in the palm domain)

As discussed elsewhere, the influenza viral RNA polymerase (EC 2.7.7.48) performs the crucial steps in the viral multiplication, i.e., it involves both in the transcription and replication processes. As RdRps are not found in mammalian cells, it is suggested that they are an excellent target for designing antiviral compounds.

1.2. Influenza Viral Transcription and Replication

Initiation of transcription is primer-dependent and the primer with the cap is snatched from nascent host mRNAs by the PB2 subunit of the polymerase by a process known as 'cap-snatching'. With the capped primer, the polymerase goes for elongation and at the end of the elongation process, the transcription is terminated at a track of five to seven U residues (a poly-U track) near the 5'-end of the vRNAs, where polyadenylation occurs by a stuttering mechanism [9]. Now the 5'-capped and 3'-tailed viral mRNAs are ready for translation by the host ribosomes in the cytoplasm.

Unlike transcription, the replication is an end-to-end synthesis of the vRNAs. The vRNAs are synthesized in two steps: in the first step, the complementary RNAs (cRNAs; (+) strands) are synthesized using the vRNAs, as templates, and in the second step, the progeny vRNAs, (-) strands, are produced using the cRNAs as templates. In the context of the polymerase, the ten nucleotides at the 5'-termini of both vRNAs and cRNAs fold back into a hook-like structure which is bound tightly in a site formed by the fingers domain of the PB1 subunit and C-terminal of the PA subunit (PA-C) [6]. The initiation of replication starts with the synthesis of a pppApG dinucleotide to the opposite nucleotide positions U₁-C₂ of the 3'-vRNA terminus. This process requires support from the priming loop, a flexible region of the PB1 subunit that protrudes into the active site of the polymerase and controls the position of the template and initial dinucleotides. It is interesting to note, that for the synthesis of cRNAs and the subsequent synthesis of progeny vRNAs, the polymerase does not follow the transcription signals and thus, the same RdRp acts in different modes during the replication and transcription processes.

Figure 3 shows a schematic diagram and suggested role(s) of the other two subunits in the transcription, replication processes. The PB2 subunit involves in the cap-snatching for initiation of transcription and the PA subunit is involved in PR and thus, maintaining genome stability. The replication mode is dependent on intracellular nuclear capsid protein (NC) concentrations. In this mode, the polymerase replicates the whole viral genome without recognizing the transcriptional signals, and the replicated genome is not capped or polyadenylated.

gRNA, genomic RNA; NC, Nuclear capsid protein (moves from the cytoplasm to nucleus through the nuclear pores), HA, Hemagglutinin, NA, Neuraminidase, PB1, PB2 & PA, polymerase subunits; M1, Matrix protein, M2, Ion channel; NSP1 & NSP2 (NEP), Non-structural proteins 1 & 2. NEP, Nuclear export protein.

Figure 3 A schematic diagram showing the proposed role(s) of each of the polymerase subunits in the production of viral mRNAs and gRNAs

In this communication, the PB1 subunit of the RNA polymerase from all the three human influenza viruses are analyzed for their active sites and reported. The catalytic metal-binding motifs already confirmed by SDM experiments and X-ray crystallographic techniques are further corroborated by the MSA analysis. Furthermore, the MSA analysis has also shown the possible catalytic amino acids involved in the nucleotide transfer reactions during the polymerization reactions. Based on these results, a catalytic mechanism for the human influenza viral polymerases is proposed.

2. Material and methods

Protein sequence data of the RNA polymerase basic protein subunit, PB1, from all three human influenza viruses, A, B and C were obtained from PUBMED and SWISS-PROT databases. The advanced version of Clustal Omega was used for protein sequence analysis. The highly conserved motifs identified by the bioinformatics analysis, and along with the data already available from biochemical, SDM and X-ray crystallographic analyses on the PB1 subunits, the possible amino acids that make up the polymerase active sites are proposed. Expasy tool was used for pI calculations of the PB1 subunits of the RNA polymerases.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. MSA Analysis of the Polymerase PB1 subunit of Influenza Virus A

Figure 4 shows the MSA of the PB1 subunits of the polymerase from several subtypes of the human influenza A virus (only the required regions for the discussions are shown here). The H1N1 subtype of the influenza A virus (Puerto Rico, 1934) is used as the standard and it showed a theoretical pI of 9.39. It is clear from Figure 4 that the PB1 subunits of influenza A viral strains from different regions are highly conserved from N- to C-terminals. Strikingly, five highly conserved motifs are identified in all the PB1 subunits of the human influenza A viral subtypes: Motif I (Finger priming loop) ⁻²³⁵KLKRR-; Motif II ⁻³⁰³TGDN³⁰⁶-; Motif III ⁻⁴⁰³LSPGMMM⁴⁰⁹GMF⁴¹²-; Motif IV ⁻⁴³⁸WDGLQSS⁴⁴⁴DDFALI⁴⁵⁰- and Motif V (end of the palm domain) ⁻⁴⁷⁴GINMSKKK⁴⁸¹SY⁴⁸³I- (highlighted in yellow, dark and light green). Several mutations in the above 5 conserved motifs from I to V of the PB1 protein were analyzed for their ability to replicate in human and chicken cells [10]. They found that replacement of the invariant amino acids, S⁴⁴⁴→P, D⁴⁴⁵→G and D⁴⁴⁶→N in motif IV -(SDD-), and K⁴⁸¹→E/T/N mutants in motif V, abolished polymerase activity completely. Furthermore, by minireplicon assays, they confirmed that any mutation altering the -SDD- sequence rendered the polymerase nonfunctional. Moreover, in human cell replication assays, they found that the Y⁴⁸³→H mutation showed only 0.5% of the activity, the N³⁰⁶→T of -GDN³⁰⁶- motif mutant showed only 2.4% of the activity and the M⁴⁰⁹→T mutant showed no activity. They suggested that such conserved residues comprising the polymerase modules may serve as potential targets for anti-influenza drugs that can attenuate infection by inhibiting influenza polymerase activity and hence, viral replication. In contrast, the natural mutation K⁴⁸⁰→R (Motif V) observed in several pandemics causing H1N1 human and swine influenza viruses, slightly increased transcription/ replication activity relative to the wild-type. The proposed amino acids in the catalytic regions and the highly conserved fingertip priming loop are highlighted in yellow. A -YAQ- triad (highlighted in yellow) was observed and a similar -YAN- triad was found to be involved in NTP selection in Severe acute respiratory syndrome-related Coronaviruses -(SARS-CoVs). The nuclear localization signals (NLSs) are highlighted in orange. The C-terminal ends in the triad -RQK in all.

3.1.1. CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of the PB1 catalytic subunits of the RdRp from influenza A viruses

sp Q07FH7 IRDRP_I96A3	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPKDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp P03431 IRDRP_I34A1	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q9Q0V0 IRDRP_I96A0	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A0M3WG62 A0A0M3WG62_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A1J0FCD5 A0A1J0FCD5_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A023M0I8 A0A023M0I8_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q0A2D9 IRDRP_I66A0	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A023M258 A0A023M258_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q2VC92 IRDRP_I80A2	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q30NP3 IRDRP_I75A0	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q910D6 IRDRP_I68A4	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp P16506 IRDRP_I68A5	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A1Z1X1S7 A0A1Z1X1S7_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q20NV3 IRDRP_I80AD	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q0A440 IRDRP_I49A1	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q0A2G8 IRDRP_I59A0	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q0A2H9 IRDRP_I83A5	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp P16511 IRDRP_I57A5	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q20PL6 IRDRP_I79A7	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q0A2F7 IRDRP_I83A4	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A1Z1X7E1 A0A1Z1X7E1_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A1Z1WYR7 A0A1Z1WYR7_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A1U9W475 A0A1U9W475_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A1U9W4I3 A0A1U9W4I3_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q0A451 IRDRP_I66A1	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q0A429 IRDRP_I56A2	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A0F6ZDR7 A0A0F6ZDR7_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A0F6WVQ6 A0A0F6WVQ6_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q0A2Q6 IRDRP_I85A3	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp P16503 IRDRP_I77AF	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q0A3Q1 IRDRP_I78AC	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp Q08II5 IRDRP_I80A6	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
sp P16513 IRDRP_I80A8	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120
tr A0A023LWC1 A0A023LWC1_9INFA	TGAPQLNPIDGFLPEDNEPSG	YAQ	FDVCLEAMAFLEESHPIFENS	CIETMEVVQQTRVD	120

		N-terminal ←	→ Fingers	
sp Q07FH7 DRDP_I96A3	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNVTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKHLDR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp P03431 DRDP_I34A1	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMIT	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q9Q0V0 DRDP_I96A0	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A0M3WG62 A0A0M3WG62_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMIT	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A1J0FCD5 A0A1J0FCD5_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A023M0I8 A0A023M0I8_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q0A2D9 DRDP_I66A0	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A023M258 A0A023M258_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q2VC92 DRDP_I80A2	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q30NP3 DRDP_I75A0	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q910D6 DRDP_I68A4	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp P16506 DRDP_I68A5	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A1Z1X1S7 A0A1Z1X1S7_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q20NV3 DRDP_I80AD	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q0A440 DRDP_I49A1	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMIT	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q0A2G8 DRDP_I59A0	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240NLS
sp Q0A2H9 DRDP_I83A5	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp P16511 DRDP_I57A5	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q20PL6 DRDP_I79A7	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q0A2F7 DRDP_I83A4	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A1Z1X7E1 A0A1Z1X7E1_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A1Z1WYR7 A0A1Z1WYR7_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A1U9W475 A0A1U9W475_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLHKK	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A1U9W4I3 A0A1U9W4I3_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLHKK	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q0A451 DRDP_I66A1	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q0A429 DRDP_I56A2	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A0F6ZDR7 A0A0F6ZDR7_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A0F6WVQ6 A0A0F6WVQ6_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q0A2Q6 DRDP_I85A3	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp P16503 DRDP_I77AF	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q0A3Q1 DRDP_I78AC	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp Q08II5 DRDP_I80A6	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
sp P16513 DRDP_I80A8	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240
tr A0A023LWC1 A0A023LWC1_9INFA	IITTHFQRKRRVR	DNMTKKMTV	QRTIGKKKQRLNKR	SYLIRALTLNMTKDA ERGKLRRA 240FPLoop
	* * * * *	* * * * *	* * * * *	* * * * *

sp Q07FH7 DRDP_I96A3	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp P03431 DRDP_I34A1	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q9Q0V0 DRDP_I96A0	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A0M3WG62 A0A0M3WG62_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A1J0FCD5 A0A1J0FCD5_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A023M0I8 A0A023M0I8_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q0A2D9 DRDP_I66A0	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A023M258 A0A023M258_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q2VC92 DRDP_I80A2	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q30NP3 DRDP_I75A0	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q910D6 DRDP_I68A4	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp P16506 DRDP_I68A5	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A1Z1X1S7 A0A1Z1X1S7_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q20NV3 DRDP_I80AD	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q0A440 DRDP_I49A1	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q0A2G8 DRDP_I59A0	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q0A2H9 DRDP_I83A5	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp P16511 DRDP_I57A5	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q20PL6 DRDP_I79A7	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q0A2F7 DRDP_I83A4	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A1Z1X7E1 A0A1Z1X7E1_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A1Z1WYR7 A0A1Z1WYR7_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A1U9W475 A0A1U9W475_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A1U9W4I3 A0A1U9W4I3_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q0A451 DRDP_I66A1	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q0A429 DRDP_I56A2	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A0F6ZDR7 A0A0F6ZDR7_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A0F6WVQ6 A0A0F6WVQ6_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q0A2Q6 DRDP_I85A3	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp P16503 DRDP_I77AF	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q0A3Q1 DRDP_I78AC	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp Q08II5 DRDP_I80A6	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
sp P16513 DRDP_I80A8	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
tr A0A023LWC1 A0A023LWC1_9INFA	TIIGDNTKWNENQNP	RMFLAMITYITRNQ	PEWFRNVL	SIAPIMFSNKMARL	GKGYMFESK 360
	* * * * *	* * * * *	* * * * *	* * * * *	* * * * *

		↑ C-terminal	
sp Q07FH7 RDRP_I96A3	ATTHSWV	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQRCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp P03431 RDRP_I34A1	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQRCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q9Q0V0 RDRP_I96A0	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A0M3WG62 A0A0M3WG62_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A1J0FCD5 A0A1J0FCD5_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A023M0I8 A0A023M0I8_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q0A2D9 RDRP_I66A0	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A023M258 A0A023M258_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q2VC92 RDRP_I80A2	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q30NP3 RDRP_I75A0	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q910D6 RDRP_I68A4	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp P16506 RDRP_I83A5	ATTHSWT	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A1Z1X1S7 A0A1Z1X1S7_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q20NV3 RDRP_I80AD	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q0A440 RDRP_I49A1	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q0A2G8 RDRP_I59A0	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q0A2H9 RDRP_I83A5	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp P16511 RDRP_I57A5	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q20PL6 RDRP_I79A7	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q0A2F7 RDRP_I83A4	ATTHSWT	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A1Z1X7E1 A0A1Z1X7E1_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A1Z1WYR7 A0A1Z1WYR7_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A1U9W475 A0A1U9W475_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A1U9W4I3 A0A1U9W4I3_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q0A451 RDRP_I66A1	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q0A429 RDRP_I56A2	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A0F6ZDR7 A0A0F6ZDR7_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A0F6WVQ6 A0A0F6WVQ6_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q0A2Q6 RDRP_I85A3	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp P16503 RDRP_I77AF	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q0A3Q1 RDRP_I78AC	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp Q08II5 RDRP_I80A6	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
sp P16513 RDRP_I80A8	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
tr A0A023LWC1 A0A023LWC1_9INFA	ATTHSWI	PKRNRISILNLSQSGILEDEQMYQKCCNLFKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVEAMVS	720
	*****	*****:***:*****:*. * .*****:*****	

//End of the PB1 subunits of the RdRp from Flu A Viruses			
sp Q07FH7 RDRP_I96A3	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp P03431 RDRP_I34A1	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFTEIMKICSTIEELRRQK-		757
sp Q9Q0V0 RDRP_I96A0	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELGRQK		757
tr A0A0M3WG62 A0A0M3WG62_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
tr A0A1J0FCD5 A0A1J0FCD5_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
tr A0A023M0I8 A0A023M0I8_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRINKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q0A2D9 RDRP_I66A0	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
tr A0A023M258 A0A023M258_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q2VC92 RDRP_I80A2	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q30NP3 RDRP_I75A0	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q910D6 RDRP_I68A4	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp P16506 RDRP_I83A5	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
tr A0A1Z1X1S7 A0A1Z1X1S7_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q20NV3 RDRP_I80AD	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q0A440 RDRP_I49A1	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q0A2G8 RDRP_I59A0	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		758
sp Q0A2H9 RDRP_I83A5	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp P16511 RDRP_I57A5	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q20PL6 RDRP_I79A7	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q0A2F7 RDRP_I83A4	RARIDARIDFESGRVKKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
tr A0A1Z1X7E1 A0A1Z1X7E1_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
tr A0A1Z1WYR7 A0A1Z1WYR7_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
tr A0A1U9W475 A0A1U9W475_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
tr A0A1U9W4I3 A0A1U9W4I3_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q0A451 RDRP_I66A1	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q0A429 RDRP_I56A2	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
tr A0A0F6ZDR7 A0A0F6ZDR7_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
tr A0A0F6WVQ6 A0A0F6WVQ6_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q0A2Q6 RDRP_I85A3	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp P16503 RDRP_I77AF	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q0A3Q1 RDRP_I78AC	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp Q08II5 RDRP_I80A6	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
sp P16513 RDRP_I80A8	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
tr A0A023LWC1 A0A023LWC1_9INFA	RARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRQK		757
	*****:*****:***:*****:*. * .*****:*****		

Figure 4 MSA of the PB1 catalytic subunits of the RdRp from human influenza A virus

Figure 5 shows the MSA of the catalytic subunits PB1 of the polymerase in different human influenza B viral strains from different regions. The standard strain, Lee 1948, showed a theoretical pI of 8.78. The subunits from various strains are completely conserved for the entire sequence with only a few amino acid changes (Fig. 5). The metal-binding regions are highlighted in dark green and the proposed amino acids in the catalytic regions and the highly conserved fingertip priming loop are highlighted in yellow. An invariant direct repeat is observed in influenza B viral strains and is marked by arrows. All the five motifs identified in influenza A viral strains are also highly conserved in the B virus: Motif I – KLKRR- Motif II –³⁰³TGDN³⁰⁶-; Motif III –⁴⁰³LSPGMMMGMF⁴¹²-; Motif IV –⁴³⁸WDGLQSSDDFAL^{F450}-; Motif V –⁴⁷⁴GINMSK^{KSYC}⁴⁸⁴- (highlighted in dark and light green) suggesting their importance in the polymerase function. The NLS region is highlighted in orange. Interestingly, the cold-adapted and wild-type strains differ only in three amino acids and are marked with stars. Among them, two are conservative replacements, whereas only one is a non-conservative type (Y→H), which is found at the C-terminal end. In influenza B virus, also the completely conserved –²²YAQ- motif (highlighted in yellow) is found as in influenza A viruses, suggesting its possible importance as in SARS-CoV-2 (YAN). Besides, a zinc-binding domain is also found in the PB1 subunits of the B viral strains in the mRNA catalytic region.

3.1.2. CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of the PB1 catalytic subunits of the RdRp from human influenza B viruses

tr A0A126TPY5 A0A126TPY5_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPEDNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120		
tr I2E0T1 I2E0T1_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr B4UQS5 B4UQS5_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A3DQQ8 A3DQQ8_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A140ERC2 A0A140ERC2_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A126TR22 A0A126TR22_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A140EMR9 A0A140EMR9_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A140EUR3 A0A140EUR3_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A126TSN3 A0A126TSN3_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A126UA37 A0A126UA37_9INFB	TGCTMI	DPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	TGCTMI	DPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A522I6 A522I6_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A4D528 A4D528_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A4D4U0 A4D4U0_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A3DRF0 A3DRF0_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A4D4V1 A4D4V1_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr B4UQB0 B4UQB0_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A4D4M4 A4D4M4_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr G7WTR6 G7WTR6_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A2D1W9N9 A0A2D1W9N9_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A2I6BBP3 A0A2I6BBP3_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A1I9TNG8 A0A1I9TNG8_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr S4S261 S4S261_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A248XLR8 A0A248XLR8_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A286NMR2 A0A286NMR2_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A0A2D1W2J9 A0A2D1W2J9_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A3DQR9 A3DQR9_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
tr A4D4X3 A4D4X3_9INFB	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	TGCTMVDPTNGPLPE	DNEP	SA	Y	Q	L	D	C	V	L	E	A	L	D	R	M	D	E	E	H	P	G	L	F	Q	A	S	Q	N	A	M	E	A	L	M	V	T	V	D	120	
	.*:**																																								

tr A0A126TPY5 A0A126TPY5_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK	GPLIKRIPMKVKDRI	SRVEYIKRALSLN	TMTKDAE	FKL	KRRA	240
tr I2E0T1 I2E0T1_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK	GPLIKRIPMKVKDRI	SRVEYIKRALSLN	TMTKDAE	FKL	KRRA	240
tr B4UQS5 B4UQS5_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK	GPLIKRIPMKVKDRI	SRVEYIKRALSLN	TMTKDAE	FKL	KRRA	240
tr A3DQQ8 A3DQQ8_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK	GPLIKRIPMKVKDRI	SRVEYIKRALSLN	TMTKDAE	FKL	KRRA	240
tr A0A140ERC2 A0A140ERC2_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK	GPLIKRIPMKVKDRI	SRVEYIKRALSLN	TMTKDAE	FKL	KRRA	240
tr A0A126TR22 A0A126TR22_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK	GPLIKRIPMKVKDRI	SRVEYIKRALSLN	TMTKDAE	FKL	KRRA	240
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK	GPLIKRIPMKVKDRI	SRVEYIKRALSLN	TMTKDAE	FKL	KRRA	240
tr A0A140EMR9 A0A140EMR9_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK	GPLIKRIPMKVKDRI	SRVEYIKRALSLN	TMTKDAE	FKL	KRRA	240
tr A0A140EUR3 A0A140EUR3_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK	GPLIKRIPMKVKDRI	SRVEYIKRALSLN	TMTKDAE	FKL	KRRA	240
tr A0A126TSN3 A0A126TSN3_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK	GPLIKRIPMKVKDRI	SRVEYIKRALSLN	TMTKDAE	FKL	KRRA	240
tr A0A126UA37 A0A126UA37_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK	GPLIKRIPMKVKDRI	SRVEYIKRALSLN	TMTKDAE	FKL	KRRA	240
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	FFSVKNI	KKKLPAK	NRK						

tr A0A126TPY5 A0A126TPY5_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr I2E0T1 I2E0T1_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr B4UQS5 B4UQS5_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A3DQQ8 A3DQQ8_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A140ERC2 A0A140ERC2_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A126TR22 A0A126TR22_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A140EMR9 A0A140EMR9_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A140EUR3 A0A140EUR3_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A126TSN3 A0A126TSN3_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A126UA37 A0A126UA37_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A5Z2I6 A5Z2I6_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A4D528 A4D528_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A4D4U0 A4D4U0_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A3DRF0 A3DRF0_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A4D4V1 A4D4V1_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr B4UQB0 B4UQB0_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A4D4M4 A4D4M4_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300REP
tr G7WTR6 G7WTR6_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A2D1W9N9 A0A2D1W9N9_9INFB	VATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A2I6BBP3 A0A2I6BBP3_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A1I9TNG8 A0A1I9TNG8_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr S4SZ61 S4SZ61_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A248XLR8 A0A248XLR8_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A286NMR2 A0A286NMR2_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A0A2D1W2J9 A0A2D1W2J9_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A3DQR9 A3DQR9_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
tr A4D4X3 A4D4X3_9INFB	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	IATAGIQIRGFVLVVENLAKNICENLEQSGLEVGGNEKKAKLSNAVAKMLSNCPGGISM	300
: *****		

tr A0A126TPY5 A0A126TPY5_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr I2E0T1 I2E0T1_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr B4UQS5 B4UQS5_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A3DQQ8 A3DQQ8_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A140ERC2 A0A140ERC2_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A126TR22 A0A126TR22_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A140EMR9 A0A140EMR9_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A140EUR3 A0A140EUR3_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A126TSN3 A0A126TSN3_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A126UA37 A0A126UA37_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A5Z2I6 A5Z2I6_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRVFLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A4D528 A4D528_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A4D4U0 A4D4U0_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A3DRF0 A3DRF0_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A4D4V1 A4D4V1_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr B4UQB0 B4UQB0_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A4D4M4 A4D4M4_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr G7WTR6 G7WTR6_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A2D1W9N9 A0A2D1W9N9_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A2I6BBP3 A0A2I6BBP3_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A1I9TNG8 A0A1I9TNG8_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr S4SZ61 S4SZ61_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A248XLR8 A0A248XLR8_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A286NMR2 A0A286NMR2_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A0A2D1W2J9 A0A2D1W2J9_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A3DQR9 A3DQR9_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
tr A4D4X3 A4D4X3_9INFB	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	TVTGDNTKWNCELNPRI FLAMTERITRDSPIWFRDFCSIAPVLFNSNKIARLGKGFMTSK	360

tr A0A126TPY5 A0A126TPY5_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr I2E0T1 I2E0T1_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr B4UQ55 B4UQ55_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A3DQ08 A3DQ08_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A140ERC2 A0A140ERC2_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A126TR22 A0A126TR22_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A140EMR9 A0A140EMR9_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A140EUR3 A0A140EUR3_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A126TSN3 A0A126TSN3_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A126UA37 A0A126UA37_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A5Z2I6 A5Z2I6_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A4D528 A4D528_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A4D4U0 A4D4U0_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A3DRF0 A3DRF0_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A4D4V1 A4D4V1_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr B4UQB0 B4UQB0_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A4D4M4 A4D4M4_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFNIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr G7WTR6 G7WTR6_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A2D1W9N9 A0A2D1W9N9_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A2I6BBP3 A0A2I6BBP3_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A1I9TNG8 A0A1I9TNG8_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr S4SZ61 S4SZ61_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A248XLR8 A0A248XLR8_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A286NMR2 A0A286NMR2_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A0A2D1W2J9 A0A2D1W2J9_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A3DQR9 A3DQR9_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
tr A4D4X3 A4D4X3_9INFB	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFSIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFNIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	TKRLKAQIPCPDLFNIPLERYNEETRAKLRKLRKLPFFNEEGTASLSPGMMMGFMNMLSTVL	420

tr A0A126TPY5 A0A126TPY5_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEEVCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr I2E0T1 I2E0T1_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEEKCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr B4UQ55 B4UQ55_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A3DQ08 A3DQ08_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A140ERC2 A0A140ERC2_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEEACMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A126TR22 A0A126TR22_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEEACMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEEACMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A140EMR9 A0A140EMR9_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEEACMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A140EUR3 A0A140EUR3_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEEACMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A126TSN3 A0A126TSN3_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEEACMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A126UA37 A0A126UA37_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A5Z2I6 A5Z2I6_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A4D528 A4D528_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A4D4U0 A4D4U0_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A3DRF0 A3DRF0_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A4D4V1 A4D4V1_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr B4UQB0 B4UQB0_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A4D4M4 A4D4M4_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr G7WTR6 G7WTR6_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A2D1W9N9 A0A2D1W9N9_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A2I6BBP3 A0A2I6BBP3_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A1I9TNG8 A0A1I9TNG8_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr S4SZ61 S4SZ61_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A248XLR8 A0A248XLR8_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A286NMR2 A0A286NMR2_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A0A2D1W2J9 A0A2D1W2J9_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A3DQR9 A3DQR9_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
tr A4D4X3 A4D4X3_9INFB	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480* (CA)
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	GVAALGIKNI GNKEYLWDGLQSSDDFALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLLGINMSKKK	480* (WT)

tr A0A126TPY5 A0A126TPY5_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr I2E0T1 I2E0T1_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr B4UQ85 B4UQ85_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A3DQQ8 A3DQQ8_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A140ERC2 A0A140ERC2_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A126TR22 A0A126TR22_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A140EMR9 A0A140EMR9_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A140EUR3 A0A140EUR3_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A126TSN3 A0A126TSN3_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A126UA37 A0A126UA37_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A5Z2I6 A5Z2I6_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A4D528 A4D528_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A4D4U0 A4D4U0_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A3DRF0 A3DRF0_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A4D4V1 A4D4V1_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr B4UQB0 B4UQB0_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A4D4M4 A4D4M4_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMEIPSFVGAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr G7WTR6 G7WTR6_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMDLPSPFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A2D1W9N9 A0A2D1W9N9_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A2I6BBP3 A0A2I6BBP3_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A1I9TNG8 A0A1I9TNG8_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr S4S261 S4S261_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A248XLR8 A0A248XLR8_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A286NMR2 A0A286NMR2_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A0A2D1W2J9 A0A2D1W2J9_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A3DQR9 A3DQR9_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
tr A4D4X3 A4D4X3_9INFB	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	SYCNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMINNGMGP	540

tr A0A126TPY5 A0A126TPY5_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr I2E0T1 I2E0T1_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr B4UQ85 B4UQ85_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A3DQQ8 A3DQQ8_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A140ERC2 A0A140ERC2_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A126TR22 A0A126TR22_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A140EMR9 A0A140EMR9_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A140EUR3 A0A140EUR3_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A126TSN3 A0A126TSN3_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A126UA37 A0A126UA37_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A5Z2I6 A5Z2I6_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A4D528 A4D528_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A4D4U0 A4D4U0_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A3DRF0 A3DRF0_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A4D4V1 A4D4V1_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr B4UQB0 B4UQB0_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A4D4M4 A4D4M4_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr G7WTR6 G7WTR6_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A2D1W9N9 A0A2D1W9N9_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A2I6BBP3 A0A2I6BBP3_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A1I9TNG8 A0A1I9TNG8_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr S4S261 S4S261_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A248XLR8 A0A248XLR8_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A286NMR2 A0A286NMR2_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A0A2D1W2J9 A0A2D1W2J9_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A3DQR9 A3DQR9_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
tr A4D4X3 A4D4X3_9INFB	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660* (CA)
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	RNLHIPEIVLKYNLMDPEYKGRLLHPQNPVFGHLSIEGIKEADITPAHGPKKMDYDAVS	660* (WT)

tr A0A126TPY5 A0A126TPY5_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr I2E0T1 I2E0T1_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr B4UQS5 B4UQS5_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A3DQQ8 A3DQQ8_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A140ERC2 A0A140ERC2_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A126TR22 A0A126TR22_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A140EMR9 A0A140EMR9_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A140EUR3 A0A140EUR3_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A126TSN3 A0A126TSN3_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A126UA37 A0A126UA37_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A522I6 A522I6_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A4D528 A4D528_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A4D4U0 A4D4U0_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A3DRF0 A3DRF0_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A4D4V1 A4D4V1_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr B4UQB0 B4UQB0_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A4D4M4 A4D4M4_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr G7WTR6 G7WTR6_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A2D1W9N9 A0A2D1W9N9_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A2I6BBP3 A0A2I6BBP3_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A1I9TNG8 A0A1I9TNG8_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr S4S261 S4S261_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A248XLR8 A0A248XLR8_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A286NMR2 A0A286NMR2_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A0A2D1W2J9 A0A2D1W2J9_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A3DQR9 A3DQR9_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
tr A4D4X3 A4D4X3_9INFB	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	GTHSWRTKRNRSIILNDRNMILEEQCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGQHSMLLEAMZHR	720

//End of the PB1 subunits from Flu B viruses

tr A0A126TPY5 A0A126TPY5_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr I2E0T1 I2E0T1_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr B4UQS5 B4UQS5_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A3DQQ8 A3DQQ8_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A0A140ERC2 A0A140ERC2_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A0A126TR22 A0A126TR22_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEVGYT	752
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A0A140EMR9 A0A140EMR9_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A0A140EUR3 A0A140EUR3_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A0A126TSN3 A0A126TSN3_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A0A126UA37 A0A126UA37_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr A522I6 A522I6_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A4D528 A4D528_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A4D4U0 A4D4U0_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A3DRF0 A3DRF0_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A4D4V1 A4D4V1_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr B4UQB0 B4UQB0_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
tr A4D4M4 A4D4M4_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT	752
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYM	752
tr G7WTR6 G7WTR6_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr A0A2D1W9N9 A0A2D1W9N9_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr A0A2I6BBP3 A0A2I6BBP3_9INFB	LKMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr A0A1I9TNG8 A0A1I9TNG8_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMVHLGEIGYI	752
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	LKMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr S4S261 S4S261_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr A0A248XLR8 A0A248XLR8_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr A0A286NMR2 A0A286NMR2_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr A0A2D1W2J9 A0A2D1W2J9_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr A3DQR9 A3DQR9_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
tr A4D4X3 A4D4X3_9INFB	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752* (CA)
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	LRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI	752* (WT)

*:*****:*****:****:*


```

sp|P19703|RDRP_INCJJ      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
sp|Q9IMP4|RDRP_INCJH      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
tr|A0A193PPL8|A0A193PPL8_9ORTO      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
tr|A0A193PPM8|A0A193PPM8_9ORTO      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
tr|A0A193PPP6|A0A193PPP6_9ORTO      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
tr|A0A193PPP0|A0A193PPP0_9ORTO      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
sp|Q6I7C3|RDRP_INCAA      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
tr|A0A193PPL7|A0A193PPL7_9ORTO      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
tr|A0A193PQ43|A0A193PQ43_INCKS      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
tr|A0A193PPP8|A0A193PPP8_INCM3      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
tr|A0A193PQ33|A0A193PQ33_INCY6      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
tr|A0A193PQ35|A0A193PQ35_9ORTO      AVNITSDNSKWNCCQPEAYLALLAYITKDSDDLMDLCSVAPVLFPCNKFVKLGQGIRLS      360
*****
    
```

```

sp|P19703|RDRP_INCJJ      NKRKTKEVI I KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
sp|Q9IMP4|RDRP_INCJH      NKRKTKEVI I KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
tr|A0A193PPL8|A0A193PPL8_9ORTO      NKRKTKEVI I KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
tr|A0A193PPM8|A0A193PPM8_9ORTO      NKRKTKEVMI KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
tr|A0A193PPP6|A0A193PPP6_9ORTO      NKRKTKEVI I KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
tr|A0A193PPP0|A0A193PPP0_9ORTO      NKRKTKEVI I KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
sp|Q6I7C3|RDRP_INCAA      NKRKTKEVI I KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
tr|A0A193PPL7|A0A193PPL7_9ORTO      NKRKTKEVI I KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
tr|A0A193PQ43|A0A193PQ43_INCKS      NKRKTKEVI I KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
tr|A0A193PPP8|A0A193PPP8_INCM3      NKRKTKEVI I KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
tr|A0A193PQ33|A0A193PQ33_INCY6      NKRKTKEVI I KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
tr|A0A193PQ35|A0A193PQ35_9ORTO      NKRKTKEVI I KAEKMGKYKNLMREEYKNLFEPLEKY IQKDVCFLPGGMLMGFMNMLSTVL      420
*****
    
```

```

sp|P19703|RDRP_INCJJ      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
sp|Q9IMP4|RDRP_INCJH      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
tr|A0A193PPL8|A0A193PPL8_9ORTO      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
tr|A0A193PPM8|A0A193PPM8_9ORTO      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
tr|A0A193PPP6|A0A193PPP6_9ORTO      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
tr|A0A193PPP0|A0A193PPP0_9ORTO      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
sp|Q6I7C3|RDRP_INCAA      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
tr|A0A193PPL7|A0A193PPL7_9ORTO      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
tr|A0A193PQ43|A0A193PQ43_INCKS      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
tr|A0A193PPP8|A0A193PPP8_INCM3      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
tr|A0A193PQ33|A0A193PQ33_INCY6      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
tr|A0A193PQ35|A0A193PQ35_9ORTO      GVSTLCYMDEELKAGCFW TGLQSSDDFVLFVAVASNWSNIHWITIRRENAVCKLIGINMSL      480
*****
    
```

```

sp|P19703|RDRP_INCJJ      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
sp|Q9IMP4|RDRP_INCJH      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
tr|A0A193PPL8|A0A193PPL8_9ORTO      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
tr|A0A193PPM8|A0A193PPM8_9ORTO      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
tr|A0A193PPP6|A0A193PPP6_9ORTO      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
tr|A0A193PPP0|A0A193PPP0_9ORTO      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
sp|Q6I7C3|RDRP_INCAA      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
tr|A0A193PPL7|A0A193PPL7_9ORTO      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
tr|A0A193PQ43|A0A193PQ43_INCKS      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
tr|A0A193PPP8|A0A193PPP8_INCM3      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
tr|A0A193PQ33|A0A193PQ33_INCY6      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
tr|A0A193PQ35|A0A193PQ35_9ORTO      EKS YGSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSI IKTNMINSNL      540
*****
    
```

```

sp|P19703|RDRP_INCJJ      NISTLHIPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
sp|Q9IMP4|RDRP_INCJH      NISTLHIPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
tr|A0A193PPL8|A0A193PPL8_9ORTO      NISTLHIPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
tr|A0A193PPM8|A0A193PPM8_9ORTO      NISTLHIPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
tr|A0A193PPP6|A0A193PPP6_9ORTO      NISTLHVPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
tr|A0A193PPP0|A0A193PPP0_9ORTO      NISTLHIPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
sp|Q6I7C3|RDRP_INCAA      NISTLHIPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
tr|A0A193PPL7|A0A193PPL7_9ORTO      NISTLHIPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
tr|A0A193PQ43|A0A193PQ43_INCKS      NISTLHIPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
tr|A0A193PPP8|A0A193PPP8_INCM3      NISTLHIPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
tr|A0A193PQ33|A0A193PQ33_INCY6      NISTLHIPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
tr|A0A193PQ35|A0A193PQ35_9ORTO      NISTLHIPEEVLKFERMDEQYRNRVFNPKNPFTNFDKTIDI FRAHGPIRVEENEAVVSTH      660
*****
    
```

//End of the PB1 catalytic subunits of the RdRp from human influenza C Viral strains		
sp P19703 RDRP_INCJJ	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
sp Q9IMP4 RDRP_INCJH	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARLESR	754
tr A0A193PPL8 A0A193PPL8_9ORTO	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PPM8 A0A193PPM8_9ORTO	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PPP6 A0A193PPP6_9ORTO	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PPP0 A0A193PPP0_9ORTO	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
sp Q6I7C3 RDRP_INCAA	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PPL7 A0A193PPL7_9ORTO	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PQ43 A0A193PQ43_INCKS	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PPP8 A0A193PPP8_INCM3	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PQ33 A0A193PQ33_INCY6	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PQ35 A0A193PQ35_9ORTO	RAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
*****.***		

P19703|RDRP_INCJJ (strain C/ JJ/1950)
 Q9IMP4|RDRP_INCJH (strain C/ Johannesburg/1/1966)
 A0A193PPL8_9ORTO (strain C/ Paris/1/1967)
 A0A193PPM8_9ORTO (strain C/ Kyoto/1/1979)
 A0A193PPP6_9ORTO (strain C/ Miyagi/8/1996)
 A0A193PPP0_9ORTO (strain C/ Yamagata/4/1992)
 Q6I7C3|RDRP_INCAA (strain C/ Ann Arbor/1/1950)
 A0A193PPL7_9ORTO (strain C/ Georgia/1/1969)
 A0A193PQ43_INCKS (strain C/ Kansas/1/1979)
 A0A193PPP8_INCM3 (strain C/ Miyagi/5/1991)
 A0A193PQ33_INCY6 (strain C/ Yamagata/1964)
 A0A193PQ35_9ORTO (strain C/ Yamagata/9/1988)

Figure 6 MSA of the PB1 catalytic subunits of the polymerase from different human influenza C viral strains

Figure 7 shows the ‘Mix and Match’ MSA of the PB1 catalytic subunits from all the three human influenza viruses. Only a few peptides show complete alignment. Interestingly, all the five motifs, Motif I ⁻²³⁵KLK/QRR- Motif II ⁻³⁰⁵TGDN-; Motif III ⁻⁴⁰⁵PGGMLMGMF-; Motif IV ⁻⁴³⁹WTGLQSSDDFVLF-; Motif V ⁻⁴⁷⁵GINMSLEKSYG- (highlighted in dark and light green) are highly conserved and aligned in all. Furthermore, a striking conservation and alignment is found in the proposed replication catalytic core in all. The proposed replication catalytic pair is highly conserved in all except an –NL- pair is found in B virus instead of a –KL- pair found in A and C viruses. The finger-priming loop in Motif-I is highly conserved in all except a Q replaces the K in C virus. However, the proposed transcription catalytic region is mostly found in the thumb regions. In contrast to the finger-priming loop which is highly conserved in all the three viruses (highlighted in yellow), the suggested priming loop (highlighted in grey) is not conserved in all but for 4 amino acids. It is interesting to note that both the catalytic metal-binding sites are preceded by an invariant hydroxy amino acid, T/S in all the three human influenza viruses, suggesting its possible role in metal-binding. Three striking differences among the subunits are, the –YAQ- triad, the –KLK- repeat and a zinc-binding motif (ZBM). The PB1 subunit of the B virus shows a typical ZBM (highlighted in orange) in the mRNA catalytic region and a –KLK- triad repeat (highlighted in grey) preceding the Met cluster at the template entry site and the –YAQ- in the N-terminal region (Fig. 7). The PB1 subunit of the A viruses show two additional metal-binding sites, one in the replication and the other in the mRNA catalytic regions.

The –YAQ- triad is found only in influenza A and B viruses which is similar to the invariant –YAN⁶⁹¹- found in SARS-CoV-1, SARS-CoV-2 and other SARS-related CoVs. It is located in the palm domain and suggested to be involved in the nucleotide selection [11,12]. The N/Q of the triad –YAN/Q- with the dual hydrogen bonding capacity can recognize the 2'-OH group of incoming NTPs and thus, discriminate NTPs and dNTPs during RNA synthesis. It is interesting to note that the YAN/Q type of motif is also found in the RdRps of Dengue, Zika, and Yellow Fever viruses too (data not shown) (11). However, it is intriguing to know that a similar triad is not found in the influenza C virus. The NLSs are found in the N-terminal region in all the three viruses and is highlighted in orange and the metal-binding regions are highlighted in dark green.

Interestingly, a completely conserved peptide with 3 to 4 Met residues, ⁻⁴⁰⁶GMMMGMX₂ML- (MxMxMX₂ML) is found in all the three human influenza viruses. This characteristic methionine-rich loop (⁻⁴⁰⁶GMMM⁴⁰⁹GMF), is found at the template entry site [Pflug et al. [6]. It is interesting to note that a similar characteristic, highly conserved methionine-rich peptide ⁻⁸⁹⁷GHMLDMYSVML- or (-X₂MX₂MX₃M-) is also found in the RdRps of SARS-CoV-1, SARS-CoV-2 and other SARS-related CoVs. This methionine-rich motif at the template entry site is suggested to be involved in stabilizing the base pair between the template and the incoming NTP [6, 11].

sp P19703 RDRP_INCJJ	TVLGVSTLCYMEDELKAKGCFWIGLQSSDD	EVLFAVASNWSNIHWTIRRFNAVCKLGIN	477
sp Q9IMP4 RDRP_INCJH	TVLGVSTLCYMEDELKAKGCFWIGLQSSDD	EVLFAVASNWSNIHWTIRRFNAVCKLGIN	477
tr A0A193PPL8 A0A193PPL8_9ORTO	TVLGVSTLCYMEDELKAKGCFWIGLQSSDD	EVLFAVASNWSNIHWTIRRFNAVCKLGIN	477
tr A0A193PPM8 A0A193PPM8_9ORTO	TVLGVSTLCYMEDELKAKGCFWIGLQSSDD	EVLFAVASNWSNIHWTIRRFNAVCKLGIN	477
tr A0A193PPP6 A0A193PPP6_9ORTO	TVLGVSTLCYMEDELKAKGCFWIGLQSSDD	EVLFAVASNWSNIHWTIRRFNAVCKLGIN	47
sp Q6I7C3 RDRP_INCAA	TVLGVSTLCYMEDELKAKGCFWIGLQSSDD	EVLFAVASNWSNIHWTIRRFNAVCKLGIN	477
tr A0A193PQ43 A0A193PQ43_INCK3	TVLGVSTLCYMEDELKAKGCFWIGLQSSDD	EVLFAVASNWSNIHWTIRRFNAVCKLGIN	477
tr A0A193PPP8 A0A193PPP8_INCM3	TVLGVSTLCYMEDELKAKGCFWIGLQSSDD	EVLFAVASNWSNIHWTIRRFNAVCKLGIN	477
tr A0A193PQ33 A0A193PQ33_INCY6	TVLGVSTLCYMEDELKAKGCFWIGLQSSDD	EVLFAVASNWSNIHWTIRRFNAVCKLGIN	477
tr A0A193PPP0 A0A193PPP0_9ORTO	TVLGVSTLCYMEDELKAKGCFWIGLQSSDD	EVLFAVASNWSNIHWTIRRFNAVCKLGIN	477
C			
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	TVLGVAAL--GIKNIGNKEYLWIGLQSSDD	FALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLGIN	475
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	TVLGVAAL--GIKNIGNKEYLWIGLQSSDD	FALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLGIN	475
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	TVLGVAAL--GIKNIGNKEYLWIGLQSSDD	FALFVNAKDEEACMEGINDFYRTCKLGIN	475
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	TVLGVAAL--GIKNIGNKEYLWIGLQSSDD	FALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLGIN	475
tr A0A024CND8 A0A024CND8_9INFB	TVLGVAAL--GIKNIGNKEYLWIGLQSSDD	FALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLGIN	475
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	TVLGVAAL--GIKNIGNKEYLWIGLQSSDD	FALFVNAKDEETCMKGINDFYRTCKLGIN	475
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	TVLGVAAL--GIKNIGNKEYLWIGLQSSDD	FALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLGIN	475
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	TVLGVAAL--GIKNIGNKEYLWIGLQSSDD	FALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLGIN	475
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	TVLGVAAL--GIKNIGNKEYLWIGLQSSDD	FALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLGIN	475
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	TVLGVAAL--GIKNIGNREYLWIGLQSSDD	FALFVNAKDEETCMEGINDFYRTCKLGIN	475
B			
sp P03431 RDRP_I34A1	TVLGVSIILNLGQKRYTKTTYWWDGLQSSDD	FALIVNAPNHEGIQAGVDRFYRTCKLGIN	476
sp Q9Q0V0 RDRP_I96A0	TVLGVSIILNLGQKRYTKTTYWWDGLQSSDD	FALIVNAPNHEGIQAGVDRFYRTCKLGIN	476
sp Q30NP3 RDRP_I75A0	TVLGVSIILNLGQKRYTKTTYWWDGLQSSDD	FALIVNAPNHEGIQAGVDRFYRTCKLGIN	476
sp P16511 RDRP_I57A5	TVLGVSIILNLGQKRYTKTTYWWDGLQSSDD	FALIVNAPNHEGIQAGVDRFYRTCKLGIN	476
sp Q0A2F7 RDRP_I83A4	TVLGVSIILNLGQKRYTKTTYWWDGLQSSDD	FALIVNAPNHEGIQAGVDRFYRTCKLGIN	476
sp P16503 RDRP_I77AF	TVLGVSIILNLGQKRYTKTTYWWDGLQSSDD	FALIVNAPNHEGIQAGVDRFYRTCKLGIN	476
sp P16513 RDRP_I80A8	TVLGVSIILNLGQKRYTKTTYWWDGLQSSDD	FALIVNAPNHEGIQAGVDRFYRTCKLGIN	476
sp Q08II5 RDRP_I80A6	TVLGVSIILNLGQKRYTKTTYWWDGLQSSDD	FALIVNAPNHEGIQAGVDRFYRTCKLGIN	476
sp Q0A3Q1 RDRP_I78AC	TVLGVSIILNLGQKRYTKTTYWWDGLQSSDD	FALIVNAPNHEGIQAGVDRFYRTCKLGIN	476
sp Q0A451 RDRP_I66A1	TVLGVSIILNLGQKRYTKTTYWWDGLQSSDD	FALIVNAPNHEGIQAGVDRFYRTCKLGIN	476
A			
*****	* .. * ****	*****	*. * * * . * .*** *.*

	Palm ←	→ Thumb	
sp P19703 RDRP_INCJJ	MSLKKSY	GSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSIIKTNMIN	537
sp Q9IMP4 RDRP_INCJH	MSLKKSY	GSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSIIKTNMIN	537
tr A0A193PPL8 A0A193PPL8_9ORTO	MSLKKSY	GSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSIIKTNMIN	537
tr A0A193PPM8 A0A193PPM8_9ORTO	MSLKKSY	GSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSIIKTNMIN	537
tr A0A193PPP6 A0A193PPP6_9ORTO	MSLKKSY	GSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSIIKTNMIN	537
sp Q6I7C3 RDRP_INCAA	MSLKKSY	GSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSIIKTNMIN	537
tr A0A193PQ43 A0A193PQ43_INCK3	MSLKKSY	GSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSIIKTNMIN	537
tr A0A193PPP8 A0A193PPP8_INCM3	MSLKKSY	GSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSIIKTNMIN	537
tr A0A193PQ33 A0A193PQ33_INCY6	MSLKKSY	GSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSIIKTNMIN	537
tr A0A193PPP0 A0A193PPP0_9ORTO	MSLKKSY	GSLPELFEFTSMFFDGEFVSNLAMELPAFTTAGVNEGVDFTAAMSIIKTNMIN	537
C			
mRNA			
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	MSKKKSY	CNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMIN	535
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	MSKKKSY	CNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMIN	535
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	MSKKKSY	CNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMIN	535
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	MSKKKSY	CNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMIN	535
tr A0A024CND8 A0A024CND8_9INFB	MSKKKSY	CNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMIN	535
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	MSKKKSY	CNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMIN	535
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	MSKKKSY	CNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMIN	535
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	MSKKKSY	CNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMIN	535
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	MSKKKSY	CNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMIN	535
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	MSKKKSY	CNETGMFEFTSMFYRDGFVSNFAMELPSFGVAGVNESADMAIGMTIIKNNMIN	535
B			
sp P03431 RDRP_I34A1	MSKKKSY	INRTGTFEFTSFFYRGGFVANFSMELPSFGVSGINESADMSIGVTVIKNNMIN	536
sp Q9Q0V0 RDRP_I96A0	MTKKKSY	INRTGTCEPTSFYRGGFVANFSMELPSFGVSGINESADMSIGVTVIKNNMMD	536
sp Q30NP3 RDRP_I75A0	MSKKKSY	INRTGTFEFTSFFYRGGFVANFSMELPSFGVSGINESADMSIGVTVIKNNMIN	536
sp P16511 RDRP_I57A5	MSKKKSY	INRTGTFEFTSFFYRGGFVANFSMELPSFGVSGINESADMSIGVTVIKNNMIN	536
sp Q0A2F7 RDRP_I83A4	MSKKKSY	INRTGTFEFTSFFYRGGFVANFSMELPSFGVSGINESADMSIGVTVIKNNMIN	536
sp P16503 RDRP_I77AF	MSKKKSY	INRTGTFEFTSFFYRGGFVANFSMELPSFGVSGINESADMSIGVTVIKNNMIN	536
sp P16513 RDRP_I80A8	MSKKKSY	INRTGTFEFTSFFYRGGFVANFSMELPSFGVSGINESADMSIGVTVIKNNMIN	536
sp Q08II5 RDRP_I80A6	MSKKKSY	INRTGTFEFTSFFYRGGFVANFSMELPSFGVSGINESADMSIGVTVIKNNMIN	536
sp Q0A3Q1 RDRP_I78AC	MSKKKSY	INRTGTFEFTSFFYRGGFVANFSMELPSFGVSGINESADMSIGVTVIKNNMIN	536
sp Q0A451 RDRP_I66A1	MSKKKSY	INRTGTFEFTSFFYRGGFVANFSMELPSFGVSGINESADMSIGVTVIKNNMIN	536
A			
mRNA			
*****	***	*****	*****

sp P19703 RDRP_INCIJ	NLSLSPSTALMALRICALQEF	FRATYRVHPWDSRVKGG	RMKIINEFIKTIENKDG	LLIADGGK	597
sp Q9IMP4 RDRP_INCIJH	NLSLSPSTALMALRICALQEF	FRATYRVHPWDSRVKGG	RMKIINEFIKTIENKDG	LLIADGGK	597
tr A0A193PPL8 A0A193PPL8_9ORTO	NLSLSPSTALMALRICALQEF	FRATYRVHPWDSRVKGG	RMKIINEFIKTIENKDG	LLIADGGK	597
tr A0A193PPM8 A0A193PPM8_9ORTO	NLSLSPSTALMALRICALQEF	FRATYRVHPWDSRVKGG	RMKIINEFIKTIENKDG	LLIADGGK	597
tr A0A193PPP6 A0A193PPP6_9ORTO	NLSLSPSTALMALRICALQEF	FRATYRVHPWDSRVKGG	RMKIINEFIKTIENKDG	LLIADGGK	597
sp Q6I7C3 RDRP_INCAA	NLSLSPSTALMALRICALQEF	FRATYRVHPWDSRVKGG	RMKIINEFIKTIENKDG	LLIADGGK	597
tr A0A193PQ43 A0A193PQ43_INCKS	NLSLSPSTALMALRICALQEF	FRATYRVHPWDSRVKGG	RMKIINEFIKTIENKDG	LLIADGGK	597
tr A0A193PPP8 A0A193PPP8_INCM3	NLSLSPSTALMALRICALQEF	FRATYRVHPWDSRVKGG	RMKIINEFIKTIENKDG	LLIADGGK	597
tr A0A193PQ33 A0A193PQ33_INCY6	NLSLSPSTALMALRICALQEF	FRATYRVHPWDSRVKGG	RMKIINEFIKTIENKDG	LLIADGGK	597
tr A0A193PPP0 A0A193PPP0_9ORTO	NLSLSPSTALMALRICALQEF	FRATYRVHPWDSRVKGG	RMKIINEFIKTIENKDG	LLIADGGK	597
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	NGMGPATAQTALQFLIADY	RYTYKCHRGDSKVEG	KRMKIKELWENTKGR	DGLLVADGGP	595
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	NGMGPATAQTALQFLIADY	RYTYKCHRGDSKVEG	KRMKIKELWENTKGR	DGLLVADGGP	595
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	NGMGPATAQTALQFLIADY	RYTYKCHRGDSKVEG	KRMKIKELWENTKGR	DGLLVADGGP	595
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	NGMGPATAQTALQFLIADY	RYTYKCHRGDSKVEG	KRMKIKELWENTKGR	DGLLVADGGP	595
tr A0A024CND8 A0A024CND8_9INFB	NGMGPATAQTALQFLIADY	RYTYKCHRGDSKVEG	KRMKIKELWENTKGR	DGLLVADGGP	595
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	NGMGPATAQTALQFLIADY	RYTYKCHRGDSKVEG	KRMKIKELWENTKGR	DGLLVADGGP	595
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	NGMGPATAQTALQFLIADY	RYTYKCHRGDSKVEG	KRMKIKELWENTKGR	DGLLVADGGP	595
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	NGMGPATAQTALQFLIADY	RYTYKCHRGDSKVEG	KRMKIKELWENTKGR	DGLLVADGGP	595
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	NGMGPATAQTALQFLIADY	RYTYKCHRGDSKVEG	KRMKIKELWENTKGR	DGLLVADGGP	595
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	NGMGPATAQTALQFLIADY	RYTYKCHRGDSKVEG	KRMKIKELWENTKGR	DGLLVADGGP	595
sp P03431 RDRP_I34A1	NDLGPATAQMALQLFIKDY	RYTYRCHR	RGDTQIQTRRSFEL	KKLWEQTRSKAGLLVSDGGP	596
sp Q9Q0V0 RDRP_I96A0	NDLGPATAQMALQLFIKDY	RYTYRCHR	RGDTQIQTRRSFEL	KKLWEQTRSKAGLLVSDGGP	596
sp Q30NP3 RDRP_I75A0	NDLGPATAQMALQLFIKDY	RYTYRCHR	RGDTQIQTRRSFEL	KKLWEQTRSKAGLLVSDGGP	596
sp P16511 RDRP_I57A5	NDLGPATAQMALQLFIKDY	RYTYRCHR	RGDTQIQTRRSFEL	KKLWEQTRSKAGLLVSDGGP	596
sp Q0A2F7 RDRP_I83A4	NDLGPATAQMALQLFIKDY	RYTYRCHR	RGDTQIQTRRSFEL	KKLWEQTRSKAGLLVSDGGP	596
sp P16503 RDRP_I77AF	NDLGPATAQMALQLFIKDY	RYTYRCHR	RGDTQIQTRRSFEL	KKLWEQTRSKAGLLVSDGGP	596
sp P16513 RDRP_I80A8	NDLGPATAQMALQLFIKDY	RYTYRCHR	RGDTQIQTRRSFEL	KKLWEQTRSKAGLLVSDGGP	596
sp Q08II5 RDRP_I80A6	NDLGPATAQMALQLFIKDY	RYTYRCHR	RGDTQIQTRRSFEL	KKLWEQTRSKAGLLVSDGGP	596
sp Q0A3Q1 RDRP_I78AC	NDLGPATAQMALQLFIKDY	RYTYRCHR	RGDTQIQTRRSFEL	KKLWEQTRSKAGLLVSDGGP	596
sp Q0A451 RDRP_I66A1	NDLGPATAQMALQLFIKDY	RYTYRCHR	RGDTQIQTRRSFEL	KKLWEQTRSKAGLLVSDGGP	596

*.:**:* *::: : ::* *:* *::: * :::: : ..***:***

sp P19703 RDRP_INCIJ	LMNNISTLHIPEEVLKFEK	MDEQYRNRVFNPKNPF	TNFDK----	TIDIFRAHGHIRVEE	652
sp Q9IMP4 RDRP_INCIJH	LMNNISTLHIPEEVLKFEK	MDEQYRNRVFNPKNPF	TNFDK----	TIDIFRAHGHIRVEE	652
tr A0A193PPL8 A0A193PPL8_9ORTO	LMNNISTLHIPEEVLKFEK	MDEQYRNRVFNPKNPF	TNFDK----	TIDIFRAHGHIRVEE	652
tr A0A193PPM8 A0A193PPM8_9ORTO	LMNNISTLHIPEEVLKFEK	MDEQYRNRVFNPKNPF	TNFDK----	TIDIFRAHGHIRVEE	652
tr A0A193PPP6 A0A193PPP6_9ORTO	LMNNISTLHVPEEVLKFEK	MDEQYRNRVFNPKNPF	TNFDK----	TIDIFRAHGHIRVEE	652
sp Q6I7C3 RDRP_INCAA	LMNNISTLHIPEEVLKFEK	MDEQYRNRVFNPKNPF	TNFDK----	TIDIFRAHGHIRVEE	652
tr A0A193PQ43 A0A193PQ43_INCKS	LMNNISTLHIPEEVLKFEK	MDEQYRNRVFNPKNPF	TNFDK----	TIDIFRAHGHIRVEE	652
tr A0A193PPP8 A0A193PPP8_INCM3	LMNNISTLHIPEEVLKFEK	MDEQYRNRVFNPKNPF	TNFDK----	TIDIFRAHGHIRVEE	652
tr A0A193PQ33 A0A193PQ33_INCY6	LMNNISTLHIPEEVLKFEK	MDEQYRNRVFNPKNPF	TNFDK----	TIDIFRAHGHIRVEE	652
tr A0A193PPP0 A0A193PPP0_9ORTO	LMNNISTLHIPEEVLKFEK	MDEQYRNRVFNPKNPF	TNFDK----	TIDIFRAHGHIRVEE	652
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	NLYNLRNLHIPEIVLKY	NLMDPEYKGRLLHPQ	NPFVGHLSIEGIKEADIT	HAHGHIRKMD	655
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	NLYNLRNLHIPEIVLKY	NLMDPEYKGRLLHPQ	NPFVGHLSIEGIKEADIT	HAHGHIVKMD	655
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	NLYNLRNLHIPEIVLKY	NLMDPEYKGRLLHPQ	NPFVGHLSIEGIKEADIT	HAHGHIVKMD	655
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	NLYNLRNLHIPEIVLKY	NLMDPEYKGRLLHPQ	NPFVGHLSIEGIKEADIT	HAHGHIVKMD	655
tr A0A024CND8 A0A024CND8_9INFB	NLYNLRNLHIPEIVLKY	NLMDPEYKGRLLHPQ	NPFVGHLSIEGIKEADIT	HAHGHIVKMD	655
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	NLYNLRNLHIPEIVLKY	NLMDPEYKGRLLHPQ	NPFVGHLSIEGIKEADIT	HAHGHIVKMD	655
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	NLYNLRNLHIPEIVLKY	NLMDPEYKGRLLHPQ	NPFVGHLSIEGIKEADIT	HAHGHIVKMD	655
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	NLYNLRNLHIPEIVLKY	NLMDPEYKGRLLHPQ	NPFVGHLSIEGIKEADIT	HAHGHIVKMD	655
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	NLYNLRNLHIPEIVLKY	NLMDPEYKGRLLHPQ	NPFVGHLSIEGIKEADIT	HAHGHIVKMD	655
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	NLYNLRNLHIPEIVLKY	NLMDPEYKGRLLHPQ	NPFVGHLSIEGIKEADIT	HAHGHIVKMD	655
sp P03431 RDRP_I34A1	NLYNIRNLHIPEVCLKWEL	MDEYQGRLCNPLNPFV	SHKEIESVNNAVMMHA	GHGPAKSM	656
sp Q9Q0V0 RDRP_I96A0	NLYNIRNLHIPEVCLKWEL	MDEYQGRLCNPLNPFV	SHKEIESVNNAVMMHA	GHGPAKSM	656
sp Q30NP3 RDRP_I75A0	NLYNIRNLHIPEVCLKWEL	MDEYQGRLCNPLNPFV	SHKEIESVNNAVMMHA	GHGPAKSM	656
sp P16511 RDRP_I57A5	NLYNIRNLHIPEVCLKWEL	MDEYQGRLCNPLNPFV	SHKEIESVNNAVMMHA	GHGPAKSM	656
sp Q0A2F7 RDRP_I83A4	NLYNIRNLHIPEVCLKWEL	MDEYQGRLCNPLNPFV	SHKEIESVNNAVMMHA	GHGPAKSM	656
sp P16503 RDRP_I77AF	NLYNIRNLHIPEVCLKWEL	MDEYQGRLCNPLNPFV	SHKEIESVNNAVMMHA	GHGPAKSM	656
sp P16513 RDRP_I80A8	NLYNIRNLHIPEVCLKWEL	MDEYQGRLCNPLNPFV	SHKEIESVNNAVMMHA	GHGPAKSM	656
sp Q08II5 RDRP_I80A6	NLYNIRNLHIPEVCLKWEL	MDEYQGRLCNPLNPFV	SHKEIESVNNAVMMHA	GHGPAKSM	656
sp Q0A3Q1 RDRP_I78AC	NLYNIRNLHIPEVCLKWEL	MDEYQGRLCNPLNPFV	SHKEIESVNNAVMMHA	GHGPAKSM	656
sp Q0A451 RDRP_I66A1	NLYNIRNLHIPEVCLKWEL	MDEYQGRLCNPLNPFV	SHKEIESVNNAVMMHA	GHGPAKSM	656

*.:**:* *::: **:*:*.*: : * ***. . . : ***: : :

sp P19703 RDRP_INCJJ	NEAVVSTHSFRTRANRTLLNTDMRAMMAEEKRYQMVCDFKSVFESADINPPIGAMSIGE	712
sp Q9IMP4 RDRP_INCJH	NEAVVSTHSFRTRANRTLLNTDMRAMMAEEKRYQMVCDFKSVFESADINPPIGAMSIGE	712
tr A0A193PPL8 A0A193PPL8_9ORTO	NEAVVSTHSFRTRANRTLLNTDMRAMMAEEKRYQMVCDFKSVFESADINPPIGAMSIGE	712
tr A0A193PPM8 A0A193PPM8_9ORTO	NEAVVSTHSFRTRANRTLLNTDMRAMMAEEKRYQMVCDFKSVFESADINPPIGAMSIGE	712
tr A0A193PPP6 A0A193PPP6_9ORTO	NEAVVSTHSFRTRANRTLLNTDMRAMMAEEKRYQMVCDFKSVFESADINPPIGAMSIGE	712
sp Q6I7C3 RDRP_INCAA	NEAVVSTHSFRTRANRTLLNTDMRAMMAEEKRYQMVCDFKSVFESADINPPIGAMSIGE	712
tr A0A193PQ43 A0A193PQ43_INCKS	NEAVVSTHSFRTRANRTLLNTDMRAMMAEEKRYQMVCDFKSVFESADINPPIGAMSIGE	712
tr A0A193PPP8 A0A193PPP8_INCM3	NEAVVSTHSFRTRANRTLLNTDMRAMMAEEKRYQMVCDFKSVFESADINPPIGAMSIGE	712
tr A0A193PQ33 A0A193PQ33_INCY6	NEAVVSTHSFRTRANRTLLNTDMRAMMAEEKRYQMVCDFKSVFESADINPPIGAMSIGE	712
tr A0A193PPP0 A0A193PPP0_9ORTO	NEAVVSTHSFRTRANRTLLNTDMRAMMAEEKRYQMVCDFKSVFESADINPPIGAMSIGE	712
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	YDAVSGTHSWRTKRNRSILNTDQRNMILEECCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGCHSMLE	715
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	YDAVSGTHSWRTKRNRSILNTDQRNMILEECCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGCHSMLE	715
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	YDAVSGTHSWRTKRNRSILNTDQRNMILEECCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGCHSMLE	715
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	YDAVSGTHSWRTKRNRSILNTDQRNMILEECCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGCHSMLE	715
tr A0A024CND8 A0A024CND8_9INFB	YDAVSGTHSWRTKRNRSILNTDQRNMILEECCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGCHSMLE	715
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	YDAVSGTHSWRTKRNRSILNTDQRNMILEECCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGCHSMLE	715
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	YDAVSGTHSWRTKRNRSILNTDQRNMILEECCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGCHSMLE	715
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	YDAVSGTHSWRTKRNRSILNTDQRNMILEECCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGCHSMLE	715
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	YDAVSGTHSWRTKRNRSILNTDQRNMILEECCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGCHSMLE	715
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	YDAVSGTHSWRTKRNRSILNTDQRNMILEECCYAKCCNLFEACFNSASYRKPVGCHSMLE	715
sp P03431 RDRP_I34A1	YDAVATTHSWIPKRNRSILNTSQRGVIEDEQMYQKCCNLFEKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVE	716
sp Q9Q0V0 RDRP_I96A0	YDAVATTHSWIPKRNRSILNTSQRGVIEDEQMYQKCCNLFEKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVE	716
sp Q30NP3 RDRP_I75A0	YDAVATTHSWIPKRNRSILNTSQRGVIEDEQMYQKCCNLFEKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVE	716
sp P16511 RDRP_I57A5	YDAVATTHSWIPKRNRSILNTSQRGVIEDEQMYQKCCNLFEKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVE	716
sp Q0A2F7 RDRP_I83A4	YDAVATTHSWIPKRNRSILNTSQRGVIEDEQMYQKCCNLFEKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVE	716
sp P16503 RDRP_I77AF	YDAVATTHSWIPKRNRSILNTSQRGVIEDEQMYQKCCNLFEKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVE	716
sp P16513 RDRP_I80A8	YDAVATTHSWIPKRNRSILNTSQRGVIEDEQMYQKCCNLFEKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVE	716
sp Q08II5 RDRP_I80A6	YDAVATTHSWIPKRNRSILNTSQRGVIEDEQMYQKCCNLFEKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVE	716
sp Q0A3Q1 RDRP_I78AC	YDAVATTHSWIPKRNRSILNTSQRGVIEDEQMYQKCCNLFEKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVE	716
sp Q0A451 RDRP_I66A1	YDAVATTHSWIPKRNRSILNTSQRGVIEDEQMYQKCCNLFEKFFPSSSYRRPVGISSMVE	716
** ***: : **::***. * : : * : * * : * * : . * * * : *		

//End of the catalytic PB1 subunits of the all three human influenza viruses A, B & C

sp P19703 RDRP_INCJJ	AIEEKLLEAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
sp Q9IMP4 RDRP_INCJH	AIEEKLLEAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARLESR	754
tr A0A193PPL8 A0A193PPL8_9ORTO	AIEEKLLEAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PPM8 A0A193PPM8_9ORTO	AIEEKLLEAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PPP6 A0A193PPP6_9ORTO	AIEEKLLEAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
sp Q6I7C3 RDRP_INCAA	AIEEKLLEAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PQ43 A0A193PQ43_INCKS	AIEEKLLEAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PPP8 A0A193PPP8_INCM3	AIEEKLLEAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PQ33 A0A193PQ33_INCY6	AIEEKLLEAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
tr A0A193PPP0 A0A193PPP0_9ORTO	AIEEKLLEAKMKRDIGAIEDSEYEEIKDIIRDAKKARIESR	754
sp P07832 RDRP_INBLE	AMAHRLRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYM-----	752
tr A0A0D6A5W0 A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB	AMAHRLRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT-----	752
tr A0A059TB43 A0A059TB43_9INFB	AMAHRLRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYT-----	752
tr A0A075CCJ9 A0A075CCJ9_9INFB	AMAHRLKMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI-----	752
tr A0A024CND8 A0A024CND8_9INFB	AMAHRLRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI-----	752
tr A0A0N7GD33 A0A0N7GD33_9INFB	AMAHRLRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI-----	752
sp O36430 RDRP_INBP9	AMAHRLRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI-----	752
tr A3DR07 A3DR07_INBBK	AMAHRLRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI-----	752
sp P13871 RDRP_INBAC	AMAHRLRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGYI-----	752
sp P13872 RDRP_INBAD	AMAHRLRMDARLDYESGRMSKDDFEKAMAHLGEIGHI-----	752
sp P03431 RDRP_I34A1	AMVSRARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFTEIMKICSTIEELRRQK-	757
sp Q9Q0V0 RDRP_I96A0	AMVSRARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELGRQK-	757
sp Q30NP3 RDRP_I75A0	AMVSRARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFSEIMKICSTIEELRRQK-	757
sp P16511 RDRP_I57A5	AMVSRARIDARIDFESGRIKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRRQK-	757
sp Q0A2F7 RDRP_I83A4	AMVSRARIDARIDFESGRVKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRRQK-	757
sp P16503 RDRP_I77AF	AMVSRARIDARIDFESGRVKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRRQK-	757
sp P16513 RDRP_I80A8	AMVSRARIDARIDFESGRVKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRRQK-	757
sp Q08II5 RDRP_I80A6	AMVSRARIDARIDFESGRVKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRRQK-	757
sp Q0A3Q1 RDRP_I78AC	AMVSRARIDARIDFESGRVKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRRQK-	757
sp Q0A451 RDRP_I66A1	AMVSRARIDARIDFESGRVKKEEFAEIMKICSTIEELRRQK-	757
* : : * : : * : : : * : : : :		

Human Influenza C Viral Strains
P19703 RDRP_INCJJ (strain C/ JJ/1950)
Q9IMP4 RDRP_INCJH (strain C/ Johannesburg/1/1966)
A0A193PPL8_9ORTO (strain C/ Paris/1/67)
A0A193PPM8_9ORTO (strain C/ Kyoto/1/1979)
A0A193PPP6_9ORTO (strain C/ Miyagi/8/1996)
Q6I7C3 RDRP_INCAA (strain C/ Ann Arbor/1/1950)
A0A193PQ43_INCKS (strain C/ Kansas/1/1979)
A0A193PPP8_INCM3 (strain C/ Miyagi/5/1991)
A193PQ33_INCY6 (strain C/ Yamagata/1964)
A0A193PPP0_9ORTO (strain C/ Yamagata/4/92)
Human Influenza B Viral Strains
P07832 RDRP_INBLE. (strain B/ Lee/1940)
A0A0D6A5W0_9INFB (strain B/ Gunma/13G022/2014)
A0A059TB43_9INFB (strain B/ Thailand/VIROAF3/2012)
A0A075CCJ9_9INFB (strain B/ Santa Cruz/761/2012)
A0A024CND8_9INFB (strain B/ Nicaragua/AGB2-12/2012)
A0A0N7GD33_9INFB. (strain B/ Hawaii/11/2015)
Q36430 RDRP_INBP9 (strain B/ Panama/45/1990)
A3DR07_INBBK. (strain B/ Bangkok/163/1990)
P13871 RDRP_INBAC. (strain B/ Ann Arbor/1/1966 [cold-adapted])
P13872 RDRP_INBAD. (strain B/ Ann Arbor/1/1966 [wild-type])
Human Influenza A Viral Subtypes
P03431 RDRP_I34A1 (strain A/ Puerto Rico/8/1934/ H1N1)
Q9Q0V0 RDRP_I96A0 (strain A/ Goose/Guangdong/1/1996/ H5N1)
Q30NP3 RDRP_I75A0 (strain A/ Beijing/39/1975/ H3N2)
P16511 RDRP_I57A5 (strain A/ Singapore/1/1957/ H2N2)
Q0A2F7 RDRP_I83A4 (strain A/ Turkey/ Ireland/ 1378/ 1983/ H5N8)
P16503 RDRP_I77AF (strain A/ Gull/Maryland/704/1977/ H13N6)
P16513 RDRP_I80A8 (strain A/ Turkey/ Minnesota/ 833/1980/ H4N2)
Q08II5 RDRP_I80A6 (strain A/ Duck/Hokkaido/8/1980/ H3N8)
Q0A3Q1 RDRP_I78AC (strain A/ Turkey/ Minnesota/ 501/1978/ H6N8)
Q0A451 RDRP_I66A1 (strain A/ Turkey/Wisconsin/1/1966/ H9N2)

Figure 7 Mix and Match MSA of the PB1 subunits of the RNA polymerases of all the three human influenza viruses

3.2. Active site Analyses of the Catalytic Subunit PB1 of Human Influenza Polymerases

3.2.1. Analyses of Metal-Binding Sites in RdRps of RNA Viral Human Pathogens

Human RNA pathogens mostly possess either (+) strand or (-) strand RNA genomes. The (+) RNA strand viruses, including the pandemic causing SARS-CoVs, are known to use two invariant Ds, one from the -A/SDD- and the other from the -GDD- motifs for catalytic metal-binding and are confirmed by SDM experiments and X-ray crystallographic techniques. For example, Sankar and Porter [13] have shown that the point mutations generated by SDM experiments in the metal-binding motif -GD³³²D- drastically affected the polymerization activity of RdRp of encephalomyocarditis virus, a small non-enveloped, (+) strand RNA virus (the causative agent of not only myocarditis and encephalitis, but also neurological diseases, reproductive disorders and diabetes in many mammalian species). Their results showed that all three amino acids of the -GDD- motif are important in maintaining the structure and function of the catalytic metal (Mg²⁺)-binding (the G in the -GDD- motif is known to generate tight bends in the structure) (Table 1).

Similar experiments have also shown that a slightly different -GDN- catalytic metal-binding motif is essential for catalysis in the (-) strand RNA viral pathogens. The (-) strand human RNA viral pathogens such as influenza, measles, mumps and respiratory syncytial viruses and Ebola virus (EBOV) also use Mg²⁺ as a co-factor for RdRp reaction. By MSA analysis, SDM experiments and minigenome assays [14] Schmidt and Hoenen, [14] have shown that -GDN- is the invariant motif in all the (-) strand RNA viral RdRps like Ebola, influenza, rabies, measles and mumps (Table 1). Furthermore, by SDM experiments, Schmidt and Hoenen [14] have confirmed that the triple mutation, -⁷⁴¹GDNQ→ -⁷⁴¹GAAA- in Ebola viral RdRp abolished both the replication as well as transcription activities. In addition to the above findings, present MSA analysis has shown that all the (-) strand RNA viral pathogens possess the invariant -GDN- in their RdRps, indicating that this motif is absolutely essential for genome replication, transcription, or both. Tchesnokov et al. [15] found that the D⁷⁴²→A mutant in the -GD⁷⁴²N- motif of Ebola viral RdRp lacked the ability to extend the primer in the presence of Mg²⁺ and hence, the Ebola viral RdRp mutant D⁷⁴²→A abolished the catalytic Mg²⁺-binding activity which resulted in the absence of polymerase activity. Similar observations were made by Schnell and Conzelmann [16] on another human pathogenic (-) strand RNA virus, viz. the rabies virus. They found by SDM experiments that any modification of the -⁷²⁸GDN- motif by conservative and non-conservative amino acids resulted in complete loss of the

RNA polymerase activity. In addition to this motif, the (-) strand RNA viral pathogens also possess a regular -G/SDD-motif as found in (+) strand RNA viral RdRps (Table 1) which provides the second D for the catalytic Mg²⁺-binding.

Metal-Binding Sites in Human Influenza Viruses

Human influenza viruses, as typical (-) strand RNA viruses, possess both the invariant catalytic Mg²⁺-binding -GDN- and -SDD- motifs in their RdRps (Table 1). These two metal-binding motifs were extensively analyzed by Biswas and Nayak [17] in human influenza A virus. They found that the -DD- in the -⁴⁴⁴SDD- motif was absolutely critical for influenza A viral polymerase activity. When either of these -DD- residues were mutated, D⁴⁴⁵→H/E, or D⁴⁴⁶→Y/N/E, the mutated PB1 polymerase subunit became nonfunctional. Furthermore, the polymerase containing an active-site mutation D445→A/D446→A (also known as PB1a) of the -⁴⁴⁴SDD- motif in influenza A virus has been used as a polymerase-negative strain in experiments [18]. When the -S⁴⁴⁴ of the above -⁴⁴⁴SDD- motif was mutated to G, modifying the sequence to -⁴⁴⁴GDD- as is found in (+) strand RNA viral RdRps, the polymerase activity was drastically reduced (1.9%), suggesting that the influenza A viral PB1 polymerase subunit cannot accommodate G in this position (Table 1). The second invariant metal-binding motif is the -GDN- motif in all (-) strand RNA viruses. When the -D³⁰⁵ in the -GD³⁰⁵N-motif was mutated to a conservative amino acid Q, it showed only feeble polymerase activity, suggesting its involvement in the metal-binding. These findings were further corroborated by the SDM analysis of the -GDN- motif of Ebola virus RdRp, again a (-) strand RNA virus like influenza viruses as discussed elsewhere. Further insights were provided by the X-ray crystallographic analysis of the influenza A viral polymerase PB1 subunit by Pflug et al. [6]. They found that the conserved active site -D³⁰⁵ of -GD³⁰⁵N- motif, together with -D⁴⁴⁵ and -D⁴⁴⁶ of the -⁴⁴⁴SDD- motif coordinate binding to metal ions and promote catalysis [6, 15]. Thus, it is clear from the above SDM experiments, X-ray crystallographic and MSA analyses that the invariant -GDN- and -SDD- are the signature metal-binding motifs in all three human influenza viral RdRps (Table 1) [19].

3.2.2. Analyses of the Catalytic Core Regions of the Polymerase Subunit PB1

In addition to the two invariant catalytic Mg²⁺-binding motifs, viz. -GDN- and -SDD-, (Fig. 7 and Table 1), all the three influenza viruses also possess two highly conserved catalytic cores. The catalytic cores consist essentially three components, viz. a template-binding pair and a catalytic amino acid for initiating catalysis by proton abstraction from 3'-OH and usually a basic amino acid at -4 to -5 position from the catalytic amino acid which has been proposed in nucleotide selection. Interestingly, two different catalytic cores are identified in human influenza viruses, suggesting one for the viral gRNA and the other for mRNA syntheses. An invariant -VG- pair is identified as the template-binding pair for the replication in all three human influenza viruses. However, the catalytic pair for the replication is found to be a -KL- in influenza A and C viruses and an -NL- for the influenza B virus. The nucleotide selection amino acid at -5 position is R/K/Q, respectively. It is interesting to note that the replication catalytic core of human influenza viruses are very similar to the other viral, prokaryotic and eukaryotic replicase enzymes (Table 2). The additional catalytic core identified in the PB1 subunits comprises of an -YG/A pair for the template-binding, a RT/NT/KL catalytic pair for initiating the catalysis and the nucleotide selection amino acid at -5 position is found to be K/N/N, respectively. The second catalytic core is similar to mRNA synthesis (Table 2), and hence could be involved in transcription.

The next conserved motif is a -KK- dyad (K⁴⁸⁰ and K⁴⁸¹), at the end of the palm domain in influenza A and B viruses. These two residues are found in the NTP entry site and are suggested to be involved in NTP binding [6]. This putative NTP tunnel directly leads to the tip of the putative priming loop which is composed of highly conserved basic residues R⁴⁵, K²³⁵, K²³⁷ and R²³⁹ (the last three amino acids form the finger-tip subdomain), -K³⁰⁸ (of the -GDNTK³⁰⁸-motif), and K⁴⁸⁰ and K⁴⁸¹ (of the palm domain) [6]. The catalytic core encompasses the polymerase active site, which is connected to the exterior by several channels, including channels for the template entry and NTPs as well as for the exit of the template and product. Near the active site, the priming loop is a feature that is essential for primer-independent initiation on the vRNA templates, but that is not required for primer-dependent transcription and, surprisingly, also not for primer-independent initiation on the cRNA templates [20] as also proposed here.

Table 1 Catalytic metal-binding sites in viral RNA-dependent RNA polymerases

Organism	Metal-binding site(s)	Method and Reference
RdRps (EC 2.7.7.48) of (+) Strand RNA Viruses		
SARS-CoV-2	-LSDD ⁷⁶¹ A- & -QGDD ⁸²⁵ Y-	X-ray [21]
SARS-CoV-1	-LSD ⁷⁶⁰ DA- & -QGDD ⁸²⁵ Y-	SDM [22]
MERS-CoV	-LSDD ⁷⁶² A- & -QGDD ⁸²⁶ Y-	By seq. similarity
Polio	----- -YGDD ³²⁹ .	X-ray [21]
Hepatitis-C	----- -NGDD ³¹⁹ .	X-ray [21]
Dengue	-YADD ⁵³³ TA- & -SGDD ⁶⁶⁴ CV-	X-ray [23]
Zika	-YADD ⁵³⁵ TA- & -SGDD ⁶⁶⁶ CV-	By seq. similarity
Yellow Fever	-YADD ²⁸⁴ TA- & -SGDD ⁴¹⁷ CV-	By seq. similarity
Rubella	-LGDD ²⁶ A- & -QGDD ⁶⁶⁷ M-	By seq. similarity
Encephalomyocarditis	----- -YG ³³² DDL-	SDM [13]
RdRps (EC 2.7.7.48) of (-) Strand RNA Viruses		
Ebola	-MG ⁷⁴¹ DNQC- & -HTSDD ⁶¹⁷ FG-	SDM [14]
Ebola	-MGD ⁷⁴² NQC- & ”	SDM [15]
Rabies	-QGD ⁷²⁹ NQV- & -LESDD ¹⁵⁸⁹ NI-	By seq. similarity
Nipah	-QGD ⁸³² NES- & -IDSDD ¹⁵²⁵ NI-	By seq. similarity
Mumps	-QGD ⁷⁷⁹ NQA- & -SSGDD ¹¹⁹⁵ KF-	By seq. similarity
Measles	-QGD ⁷⁷³ NQT- & -AYGDD ¹²⁵⁶ DS- & -LIGDD ¹⁴⁷⁰ D- & -ESDED ¹⁵⁹⁸ V-	By seq. similarity
RdRps (EC 2.7.7.48) of (-) Strand Segmented RNA Viruses		
Influenza A	-TGD ³⁰⁵ N TK- & -QSSDD ⁴⁴⁶ FA-	SDM [17]
Influenza B	-TGD ³⁰⁵ N TK- & -QSSDD ⁴⁴⁵ FA-	By seq. similarity
Influenza C	-TGD ³⁰⁷ N SK- & -QSSDD ⁴⁵¹ FV-	By seq. similarity

Adapted from Palanivelu [11]

Table 2 Catalytic region(s) in the viral, prokaryotic and eukaryotic (nuclear and organellar) polymerases

Polymerase Type	Catalytic Region(s)
SSU RNA and DNA Polymerases	
Viral T7 SSU RNA pol	- ⁸²⁰ WLAY- ⁸ GVTR- ⁴ SVT ⁸³¹ R ¹ SVMTLA ⁸³⁹ G ⁹ S- [24]
Viral SP6 SSU RNA Pol	- ⁶¹² WDSI- ⁸ GITR- ⁴ SLTKK ¹ PVMTLPY ⁸ GS-
Mitochondrial SSU RNA pol (Yeast)	-TR- ⁴ KVVKQ ¹ TVMTNVY ⁸ GV--
Chloroplast SSU pol (ARATH)	-DR- ⁴ KLVKQ ¹ TVMTSVY ⁸ GV-
<i>E. coli</i> DNA pol I (SSU)	- ⁷⁵³ CR- ⁴ RSAK ⁷⁵⁸ A ¹ INFGLI ⁸ GM- [25]
Initiation Subunits of Prokaryotic and Eukaryotic MSU DdRps (mRNAs)	
<i>E. coli</i> MSU RNAP β subunit	- ⁵³⁹ TR- ⁸ ERAGFEV RD 1VHPH ^Y 7GRV ⁵⁵⁸ -
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> MSU RNAP II Rpb2 subunit	- ⁸⁵¹ FR- ⁵ SLFFRS ¹ YMDQEKK ^Y 9GMSI ⁸⁷⁰ -
Human MSU RNAP II Rpb2 subunit	- ⁸⁰⁶ FR- ⁵ SVFYRS ¹ YKEQESK ^K 9GFDQ ⁸²⁵ -
Elongation Subunits of Prokaryotic and Eukaryotic MSU DdRps (mRNAs)	
<i>E. coli</i> MSU RNAP β' subunit	- ⁸³³ NSV- ⁶ DAVKVRS ¹ VVSC ⁵ DTDFGVC ¹² AHC ¹⁵ Y ¹⁶ G ¹⁷ RDL ⁸⁶¹ -
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> MSU RNAP II Rpb1 subunit	- ⁵⁵ DPR- ⁶ LGSIDRN ¹ LKC ⁴ QTC ⁷ QEGMNEC ¹⁴ PGHF ¹⁸ G ¹⁹ H ¹⁸⁴ -
Human MSU RNAP II Rpb1 subunit	- ⁵⁹ DPR- ⁶ QGVIER ^T GRC ⁴ QTC ⁷ AGNMTEC ¹⁴ PGHF ¹⁸ G ¹⁹ H ¹⁸⁸ -
Active Site Regions in Prokaryotic and Eukaryotic DNA Polymerases#	
T7 DNA polymerase (Rep)	- ⁸²² AYGVTR- ⁴ SVT ⁸³¹ R ¹ SVMTLA ⁸³⁹ G ⁹ SKEFG [26]
<i>P. furiosus</i> DNA polymerase	- ⁴⁷⁸ ILLDYR- ⁵ QKAIKL ¹ LANSFY ⁷ GYYGYAK-
Yeast DNA polymerase α (Rep)	- ⁹³³ RVQCDIR- ⁵ QQALKL ¹ TANSMY ⁷ GCLGYVN-
Human DNA polymerase α (Rep)	- ⁹³⁹ ILQYDIR- ⁵ QKALKL ¹ TANSMY ⁷ GCLGFSY-
Human DNA polymerase δ (Rep) (Catalytic subunit)	- ⁶⁶³ RQVLDGR- ⁵ QLALKV ¹ SANSVY ⁷ GFTGAQV-
Human DNA polymerase ε (Rep) (Catalytic subunit)	- ⁸⁰¹ YDSLQ- ⁴ LAHKC ¹ ILNSFY ⁷ GVVMR-
Yeast DNA polymerase ε (Rep) (Catalytic subunit)	- ⁸¹⁶ YDSLQ- ⁴ LAHKV ¹ ILNSFY ⁸³¹ G ⁸ YVMR- [27]
Human DNA polymerase γ (Rep)	- ⁹¹⁷ TTVGISR- ⁴ EHAKI ¹ FNYGRIY ⁸ GAGQPFAER-
(+) Strand RNA Viruses- (SARS-Coronaviruses)	
RdRps (NSP12)	
SARS-CoV-1	-STMTNR- ⁵ QFHQKL ¹ LKSIAATRGATWIGTSKFY ²¹ GG ⁵⁹⁷ -
SARS-CoV-2	-STMTNR- ⁵ QFHQKL ¹ LKSIAATRGATWIGTSKFY ²¹ GG ⁵⁹⁷ - [13]
MERS-CoV	-STMTNR- ⁵ QYHQKM ¹ LKSMAATRGATCVIGTTKFY ²¹ GG ⁵⁹⁸ -
(-) Strand RNA Viruses- (Human Influenza Viruses)	
PB1 Catalytic Subunits of the RdRps	
Human influenza A virus	- ²⁵⁶ ETLAR- ⁵ SICEKL ¹ EQSGLPV ⁸ GGN- gRNA - ⁴⁷⁷ MSKKK- ⁵ SYINRT ¹ GTFEFTSFFRY ¹³ GFV- mRNA#
Human influenza B virus	- ²⁵⁶ ENLAK- ⁵ NICENL ¹ EQSGLPV ⁸ GGN- gRNA - ⁶⁶⁶ RTKRN- ⁵ RSILNT ¹ DQRNMILEEQCY ¹³ AKCCX ₆ CF- mRNA#
Human influenza C virus	- ²⁵⁸ ETVAQK- ⁴ ICEKL ¹ KESGLPV ⁸ GGN- gRNA - ⁴⁶⁴ IRRFN- ⁴ AVCKL ¹ IGINMSLEKSY ¹² GSL- mRNA#

Adapted from Palanivelu [11,27].

gRNA, genomic RNA; Rep, Replicase. *P. furiosus*, *Pyrococcus furiosus*; The amino acids confirmed by SDM and by other techniques in the active sites are highlighted in dark blue; *The catalytic region of the human influenza viruses is arrived at by sequence similarity with other DNA/RNA polymerases. In the human influenza viruses, two such possible catalytic regions are found: one similar to RNA polymerases may involve in transcriptions and the other one similar to SSU DNA/RNA polymerases and eukaryotic replicases may involve in viral genome replications.

Table 3 shows the effect of mutations in SDM and natural mutations in the conserved motifs of the PB1 catalytic subunit of the human influenza A virus and their effects on polymerase activity/ replicative ability in human cells.

Table 3 Effect of mutations by SDM and natural mutations in the conserved motifs of the polymerase subunit PB1

Metal-binding site	Polymerase activity (%)	Reference
Metal-Binding Site-1 (-⁴⁴⁴SDD-)		
⁴⁴⁵ D/ ⁴⁴⁶ D→A	0	[18]
⁴⁴⁴ S→G	1.9	[17]
⁴⁴⁵ D→H/E	0	[17]
⁴⁴⁶ D→Y/N/E	0	[17]
⁴⁴⁴ S→P	0	[10]
⁴⁴⁵ D→G	0	[10]
⁴⁴⁶ D→N	0	[10]
Metal-Binding Site-2 (-³⁰⁴GDN-)		
⁻³⁰⁵ D→Q	Feeble	[17]
⁻³⁰⁶ N→T	2.4	[10]
Metal-Binding Site-2 (-⁷⁴¹GDNQ-), Ebola virus- a (-) Strand RNA virus		
⁻⁷⁴¹ GDNQ→ ⁷⁴¹ GAAA	0	[14]
⁻⁷⁴² D→A	0	[15]
Polymerase Active Site		
⁴⁷⁶ N→L/ ⁴⁷⁷ M→T (DM)	0	[10]
⁴⁷⁶ N→T/ ⁴⁷⁸ S→T (DM)	0	[10]
⁴⁷⁸ S→T/R	0	[10]
⁴⁸⁰ K→R	117.2	[10]
⁴⁸¹ K→E/T/N	0	[10]
⁴⁸³ Y→H	0.5	[10]

4. Proposed Mechanism of Action of the Polymerase Catalytic Subunit PB1 of Human Influenza Viruses

It is interesting to note that all DNA and RNA polymerases, irrespective of their sources, possess not highly conserved active sites but also very similar 3D structures, suggesting a similar catalytic mechanism [4, 28,29]. The finding that the PB1 subunit alone could transcribe RNA templates *in vitro*, suggested it possessed all the required active sites to synthesize a new strand of RNA from vRNA templates and possesses similar active sites and 3D structure [6, 30, 31].

A minimal number of steps involved in the catalytic cycle of the DNA/RNA polymerases are i) NTP selection and Watson-Crick base pairing with the complementary nucleotide to the template, ii) Addition of the nucleotide to the growing primer, iii) Inorganic pyrophosphate formation and iv) Restoration of the active site and translocation.

The catalysis is initiated by the proton abstraction by the catalytic amino acid from the 3'-OH of the primer, which is followed by an electrophilic-nucleophilic attack between the α -phosphate of the Watson-Crick base-paired NTP at the active site and the 3'-Oxyanion of the growing primer, resulting in the phosphodiester bond formation with the subsequent release of pyrophosphate. The proton abstracted in the first step is transferred to the pyrophosphate resulting in the formation of inorganic pyrophosphate (ppi). The active site is restored and translocated for the next addition.

Based on the data available, Figs. 8 and 9 describe plausible mechanisms of action of the PB1 polymerase subunits of the human influenza viruses.

Figure 8 Proposed steps in the replication of viral genomic RNAs

Figure 9 Proposed steps in the transcription of viral mRNAs

- Step 1.** Enzyme with the Watson-Crick base-paired NTP at the Entry Site: In replication, the initiation step of RNA synthesis begins at the 3'- end of the vRNA template by means of a *primer-independent* mechanism. The primer-independent initiation consists in the addition of a GTP to the 3'-OH of the first initiating ATP and is followed by the next base (Fig. 8). Viral mRNA synthesis is *primer-dependent* and the primer is obtained from the host mRNAs by the cap-snatching method using the PB2 subunit. The primer is base-paired with the U at the 3' end of the viral RNA. The Y residue in the YG template-binding pair is suggested to be involved in base stacking as well as hydrogen bonding to the ribose moiety at the 3'- growing end and the G provides the necessary kink for the effective positioning with the template. The catalytic site amino acid R⁴⁸⁶ is positioned near the 3'- growing end for proton abstraction. The invariant K⁴⁸¹ is shown to be involved in the NTP selection.

(The epsilon group of K⁴⁸¹ could form the necessary hydrogen bonds with the substrate in the ternary complex). The catalytic Mg²⁺ is shown coordinating with the catalytic D⁴⁴⁵ and D⁴⁴⁶, D³⁰⁵ shielding the β- and γ- phosphates of the incoming NTP and exposing the α-phosphate to the electrophilic- nucleophilic attack at the polymerizing site (Figs. 8 and 9).

- **Step 2.** Proton abstraction by the active site amino acid K²⁶⁵ (R⁴⁸⁶ in transcription site) with the simultaneous electrophilic-nucleophilic attack at the polymerase site. Formation of phosphodiester bond between the 3'-Oxyanion and the α-phosphate of the NTP.
- **Step 3.** Proton transfer from the active site amino acid K²⁶⁵ (R⁴⁸⁶ in transcription site) to the pyrophosphate and formation of inorganic pyrophosphate.
- **Step 4.** Restoration of the active site and translocation of the enzyme to the next nucleotide (Figs. 8 and 9).

5. Conclusions

The human influenza viral RNA polymerase is a heterotrimeric enzyme and made up of three different subunits, viz. two basic protein subunits (PB1 and PB2) and an acidic protein subunit (PA). The PB1 polymerase subunits of the viruses contain the active sites for nucleotide polymerization and perform the synthesis of both the mRNAs and gRNAs. The two typical invariant catalytic metal-binding motifs, viz. –GDN and –SDD- reported in (-) strand RNA viruses are also found in the PB1 polymerase subunits. Furthermore, MSA analysis shows two possible catalytic regions in the polymerase PB1 catalytic subunits from all the three human influenza viruses. The two possible catalytic regions suggest that the polymerase may follow a dual mode, i.e., it could use one for mRNA synthesis (transcription) and the other for viral gRNA synthesis (replication) depending upon its association to the cap-snatching PB2 (for mRNA synthesis, transcription) or its association with the proofreading PA subunit for gRNA synthesis (replication). It could use the same metal-binding motifs for both the mRNA and gRNA syntheses. Thus, all the three human influenza viruses exhibit common and distinct features among them. These data throw more light on the functioning of the key enzyme and may help in designing structure-based antiviral drugs targeting the PB1 subunit's active sites for the treatment of flu in the future.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The author wishes to thank Dr. H. Shakila, Professor and Head, Department of Molecular Microbiology, School of Biotechnology, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai, for useful suggestions on the manuscript.

References

- [1] Dangi T, Jain A. Influenza Virus: A Brief Overview. *Proc Natl Acad Sci (USA)*. 2012; 82:111–121. DOI 10.1007/s40011-011-0009-6.
- [2] Guo Y, Jin F, Wang P, Wang M, Zhu JM. Isolation of Influenza Virus C from pigs and experimental infection of pigs with influenza C virus. *J Gen Virol*. 1983; 64:177-182.
- [3] Su S, Fu X, Li G, Kerlin F, Veit M. Novel Influenza D virus: Epidemiology, pathology, evolution and biological characteristics, *Virulence*. 2017; 8:1580-1591.
- [4] Palanivelu P. Identification of HNH Endonuclease Domain in the Basic Protein 2 Subunit of the Polymerase of Human Influenza Viruses, *World J of Rec Res Rev*. 2022; 15: 425–442.
- [5] P Palanivelu Identification of DEDD- and PHP-Superfamilies of Proofreading Exonucleases in the Acidic Protein Subunit PA of RNA Polymerase of Human Influenza Viruses, *World J Rec Res Rev*. 2022; 16: 804–824.
- [6] Pflug A, Guilligay D, Reich S, Cusack S. Structure of influenza A polymerase bound to the viral RNA promoter. *Nature*. 2014;516:355–360.
- [7] Hengrung N, El Omari K, Martin IS, Vreede FT, Cusack S, Rambo RP, Vornrhein C, et al. Crystal structure of the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase from influenza C virus. *Nature*. 2015;527: 114-118
- [8] Fan H, Walker AP, Carrique L, Keown JR, Martin IS, Karia D, Sharps J, Hengrung N, Pardon E, Steyaert J, Grimes JM, Fodor E. Structures of influenza A virus RNA polymerase offer insight into viral genome replication. *Nature*. 2019; 573:287-295.
- [9] Poon LLM, Pritlove DC, Fodor E, Brownlee GG. Direct evidence that the poly(A) tail of influenza A virus mRNA is synthesized by reiterative copying of a U track in the virion RNA template. *J Virol*. 1999; 73:3473–3476.

- [10] Chu C, Fan S, Li C, Macken C, Kim JH, Hatta M, et al. Functional Analysis of Conserved Motifs in Influenza Virus PB1 Protein. PLoS ONE. 2012; 7: e36113, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0036113
- [11] Palanivelu P. RNA-Dependent RNA Polymerases of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome-Related Coronaviruses- An Insight into their Active Sites and Mechanism of Action. Int J Biochem Res Rev. 2020; 29: 29-52.
- [12] Hillen HS, Kokic G, Farnung L, Dienemann C, Tegunov D, Cramer P. Structure of replicating SARS-CoV-2 polymerase. bioRxiv preprint. 2020; doi.org/10.1101/2020.04.27.063180. April 27.
- [13] Sankar S, Porter AG. Point mutations which drastically affect the polymerization activity of encephalomyocarditis virus RNA-dependent RNA polymerase correspond to the active site of *Escherichia coli*. DNA polymerase I. J Biol Chem. 1992; 267:10168–10176.
- [14] Schmidt ML, Hoenen T. Characterization of the catalytic center of the Ebola virus L polymerase. PLoS Negl Trop Dis. 2017;11:1-14.
- [15] Tchesnokov EP, Raesisimakiani P, Ngure M, Marchant D, Götte M. Recombinant RNA-Dependent RNA Polymerase Complex of Ebola Virus. Sci Rep. 2018; 8:3970-3979.
- [16] Schnell MJ, Conzelmann KK. Polymerase activity of in vitro mutated rabies virus L protein. Virology. 1995; 214:522-530. doi: 10.1006/viro.1995.0063.
- [17] Biswas SK and Nayak DP. Mutational Analysis of the Conserved Motifs of Influenza A Virus Polymerase Basic Protein 1. J Virol. 1994; 68:1819-1826.
- [18] Vreede FT, Jung TE, Brownlee GG. 2004. Model suggesting that replication of influenza virus is regulated by stabilization of replicative intermediates. J Virol. 78:9568–9572. doi: 10.1128/JVI.78.17.9568-9572.2004.
- [19] Poch O, I Sauvaget, M Delarue, N Tordo. 1989. Identification of four conserved motifs among the RNA-dependent polymerase encoding elements. EMBO J. 8:3867-3874.
- [20] te Velthuis AJW, Fodor E. Influenza virus RNA polymerase: insights into the mechanisms of viral RNA synthesis. Nat Rev Microbiol. 2016; 14: 479–493.
- [21] Gao Y, Yan L, Huang Y, Liu F, Zhao Y, Cao L, Wang T, et al. Structure of the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase from COVID-19 virus. Science. 2020: 368:779-782.
- [22] Subissia L, Posthumab CC, Colleta A, Dobbeeb JCZ, Gorbalenyab AE, Decrolya E, Snijderb EJ, Canarda B, Imberta I, One severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus protein complex integrates processive RNA polymerase and exonuclease activities. Proc Natl Acad Sci (USA). 2014; E3900–E3909.
- [23] Yap TL, Xu T, Chen YL, Malet H, Egloff MP, Canard B, Vasudevan SG, Lescar J. Crystal Structure of the Dengue Virus RNA-Dependent RNA Polymerase Catalytic Domain at 1.85-Angstrom Resolution. J Virol. 2007, 81: 4753–4765.
- [24] Palanivelu P. Single Subunit RNA Polymerases: An Insight into their Active Sites and Catalytic Mechanism, In: Adv Trends Biotechnol Genet. Vol 1, pp 1-38, SCIENCEDOMAIN International Book Publishers, UK. ISBN: 978-93-89246-59-9, DOI:10.9734/bpi/atbg/v1; (2019).
- [25] Palanivelu P. DNA polymerases – An insight into their active sites and mechanism of action, In: Rec Adv Biol Res. Vol. 1, pp 1-39, SCIENCEDOMAIN International Book Publishers, UK. ISBN: 9788193422441, DOI: 10.9734/bpi/rabr/v1; (2019).
- [26] Maksimova TG, Mustayev AA, Zaychikov EF, Lyakhov DL, Tunitskaya VL, Akbarov AK, Luchin SV, et al, Lys631 residue in the active site of the bacteriophage T7 RNA polymerase. Affinity labeling and site-directed mutagenesis. Eur J Biochem. 1991;195:841-847.
- [27] Palanivelu P. An Insight into the Mechanism of Genome Duplication in Eukaryotes: Polymerase and Proofreading Functions by Eukaryotic DNA Replicases. Int J Rec Sci Res. 2022; 13:2076-2116.
- [28] Palanivelu P. Multi-subunit RNA Polymerases of eubacteria - An insight into their active sites and catalytic mechanism. Indian J Sci Technol. 2018; 11:1-37 DOI: 10.17485/ijst/2018/v11i39/131802; 2018.
- [29] Palanivelu P. Eukaryotic Multi-subunit DNA dependent RNA Polymerases: An Insight into their Active Sites and Catalytic Mechanism. In: Adv Trends in Biotechnol Genet. Vol. 1, pp 1-38. SCIENCEDOMAIN International Book Publishers, UK, ISBN: 978-93-89246-59-9, DOI:10.9734/bpi/atbg/v1; (2019).
- [30] Kobayashi M, T Toyoda, A Ishihama. 1996. Influenza virus PB1 protein is the minimal and essential subunit of RNA polymerase. Arch Virol. 141:525–539.
- [31] Toyoda T, Kobayashi M, Nakada S, Ishihama A. Molecular dissection of influenza virus RNA polymerase: PB1 subunit alone is able to catalyze RNA synthesis. Virus Genes. 1996;12:155-63.